

CIRCEE, the CIRCular Energy Economy model

Bridging the gap between economic and industrial ecology concepts

Darius Corbier^{1,2}

¹CMCC Foundation - Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change, Lecce, Italy

²RFF-CMCC European Institute on Economics and the Environment, Milan, Italy

³Environmental Change Institute, Oxford Centre for the Environment, Oxford University, Oxford, UK

⁴Geography and Environment, Loughborough University, Loughborough, UK

Correspondence

Darius Corbier, RFF-CMCC European Institute on Economics and the Environment (EIEE), Via Bergognone 34, Milan, 20144 MI, Italy.
Email: darius.corbier@cmcc.it

Editor Managing Review: Cristina Madrid

Present address

Darius Corbier, RFF-CMCC European Institute on Economics and the Environment (EIEE), Via Bergognone 34, Milan, MI, 20144, Italy.

Funding information

HORIZON EUROPE Climate, Energy and Mobility, Grant/Award Numbers: 101056868, 101081604; Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, Grant/Award Number: 870245

Abstract

Transitioning to a circular economy (CE) can contribute to the achievement of long-term climate targets. A comprehensive evaluation of CE strategies requires a macro-level approach that integrates environmental, social, and economic goals. Policy support, behavioral changes, innovation, and new business models play key roles in this transition. Additionally, understanding the potential synergies, benefits, and trade-offs associated with these strategies is essential for their effective implementation. This paper proposes a novel approach, using macroeconomic modeling, industrial ecology, and behavioral concepts to evaluate the impacts of CE strategies on socioeconomic and climate systems. As an application, the paper investigates the environmental and economic effects in Japan of increasing the extended producer responsibility (EPR) fee on energy-using durable goods. We show that increasing the fee makes households substitute conventional goods for circular services. Also, while increasing EPR fees for energy-using durable goods may decrease the materials needed to produce and operate these goods, the overall impact on sustainability goals is rather low.

KEYWORDS

circular economy, emission mitigation, extended producer responsibility, industrial ecology, lifestyle changes, macroeconomic model

1 | INTRODUCTION

One promising vision for sustainability, while not yet an established fact, is by shifting from a linear economic system to a circular one (de Oliveira & Oliveira, 2023, IPCC, 2023, Lu et al., 2024, Pauliuk et al., 2021, Schroeder et al., 2019, Serrano et al., 2021, Takimoto et al., 2024). Pauliuk et al. (2021) point out for a more efficient use of materials and the formulation of global dematerialization scenarios in models. Schroeder et al. (2019) conclude that a circular economy (CE) has the potential to help countries achieve specific SDG goals. The last IPCC (2023) report recognizes the important role that the CE plays in countries' transition to net zero in the long run. CE strategies such as green product design (Aguilar Esteva et al., 2021), closed-loop systems (van der Laan & Aurisicchio, 2020) and extended producer responsibility (EPR) can help reduce the carbon footprint of industries and products (IPCC, 2023) while creating new business opportunities, enhancing resource security (Lee & Cha, 2020, and Markevych et al., 2022), and reducing the impact of resource price volatility on economies (Gaustad et al., 2018). This shift can lead to significant environmental

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2024 The Author(s). *Journal of Industrial Ecology* published by Wiley Periodicals LLC on behalf of International Society for Industrial Ecology.

benefits, including reduced greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, lower energy and material consumption, and improved resource efficiency. Nonetheless, the shift can also lead to potential trade-offs as pointed out by Korhonen et al. (2018), Blomsma and Brennan (2017), Leipold et al. (2023) and Schroeder et al. (2019). Korhonen et al. (2018) identify limits and challenges for the CE that need to be addressed when assessing the impact of the strategies on the environment. Schroeder et al. (2019) show that trade-offs exist between different SDG goals when implementing CE strategies. Leipold et al. (2023) provide different research priorities for the study of CE strategies, one of them being the identification of trade-offs caused by CE strategies implementation and the tools to minimize them.

Assessing the full potential of a CE requires a macro-level and integrated assessment approach that addresses the complex inter-dependencies and trade-offs between environmental, social, and economic objectives (McCarthy et al., 2018). Policy support (Hartley et al., 2020), behavioral elasticities and the corresponding lifestyle changes (Parajuly et al., 2020, Szilagyi et al., 2022, and Shevchenko et al., 2023), innovation, and new business models such as sharing and digitalization are key enablers for the transition to a CE (Chauhan et al., 2022). Assessing the impact of a CE on socio-economic systems remains a complex and challenging task for integrated assessment models (IAMs) and the macroeconomic modeling community. Pauliuk et al. (2017) emphasize the necessity of incorporating industrial ecology system linkages into IAMs. Unequivocally, the controversy that opposed Georgescu-Roegen/Dally and Solow/Stiglitz in the last century (Couix, 2019, and Germain, 2019) has never been as important as today as the climate modeling community seeks to integrate concepts from industrial ecology.

The literature on the study of CE in macroeconomic models and in IAMs that use within their core economic module different macroeconomic modeling approaches is still scarce, although some exist. We provide hereafter a literature review of the main studies that use different types of macroeconomic models to assess CE strategies. Masui (2005) and Okushima and Yamashita (2005) use a computable general equilibrium (CGE) to analyze waste management policies in Japan. Masui (2005) highlights the importance of increased R&D investment in waste treatment technologies to stimulate recycling and reuse activities, without weighing on GDP. Okushima and Yamashita (2005) find that the introduction of industrial waste tax in Japan effectively reduced the total amount of final waste disposal without significantly affecting growth. Pittel et al. (2010) developed an analytical general equilibrium model to study the macroeconomic impacts of recycling. They show that the existence of a waste market and the implementation of subsidies can achieve optimality in a general equilibrium where recycling is low under market failures. Kinnaman and Yokoo (2011) and Yokoo and Kinnaman (2013), via a general equilibrium model, show analytically that e-waste taxes, subsidies for e-waste return, and import taxes in developing countries can lead to global economic efficiency. Akimoto and Futagami (2018) use a Ramsey-type model with a recycling firm to analytically show how different public policies (consumption tax and subsidy to recycling activities) can help an economy transition toward a CE. Bongers and Casas (2022) use a dynamic general equilibrium model for the EU-27 to assess the optimal recycling rate. They show that the CE can foster sustainable economic growth, and technological changes aimed at reducing recycling costs significantly improve the circularity of an economy. Finally, a shock on the evolution of the relative price of secondary materials to primary materials could do more harm to growth than would be beneficial to the CE. Lafforgue and Rouge (2019), via a growth model with endogenous technical change toward recycling, show analytically the optimal path of R&D investments in recycling technologies. The economy will increase the use of primary resources prior to a breakthrough event. Nechifor et al. (2020), via the model ENGAGE-materials, assess the impact of using more steel scrap in industries in China. They show a significant impact on GDP exists if incentives for recycling practices are increased and downstream sectors are more adaptable to steel scrap. Grüning et al. (2021), via a multi-sector dynamic general equilibrium model for the Lithuanian economy, find multiple trade-offs exist with respect to trade, circularity, environment, and economic growth. In particular, a higher price of primary resources, a positive shock on the arrival rate of technology, and a high rate of refurbished goods resolve the existing trade-off. Argentiero et al. (2022), via a DSGE model augmented with recycling behaviors for the EU-27, show that behavioral policies have a positive impact on recyclable consumption. They also highlight the importance of increasing R&D investments in the recyclability of consumer goods. Lahcen et al. (2022), via a supply-chain general equilibrium model for Belgium's Coca Cola firm, show that specific policies can reduce the use of primary materials if the general opinion sees circular products as good substitutes for conventional products. The degree of substitutability between conventional and circular products plays an important role in driving policy outcomes.

Other studies explore the sharing economy and the extension of product lifetimes at the macro level. Oh (2019) uses a general equilibrium model for the United States to show that the second-hand market for durable goods is an important driver of the depreciation path of these goods. Ordóñez-de Haro et al. (2019) study the macroeconomic impacts of sharing durable goods with a general equilibrium model. The authors find that positive productivity shocks have a beneficial impact on the sharing sector as they increase the number of goods owned by households that can be shared. Razeghian and Weber (2019b) develop an overlapping generation model to study the impact of sharing markets on product prices and design to increase durability. They study the strategic choices a firm can make to engage in green product design to increase the durability of goods in the presence of a sharing market. Zhou and Smulders (2021), via an endogenous growth model augmented with a refurbishing sector, demonstrate that the promotion of reuse and refurbishment can divert investment away from increased innovations in green product design. The authors highlight the important role played by technical change in creating new and more efficient products, and in avoiding a potential crowding out effect. Brusselaers et al. (2022) assess the economy-wide effects of the CE in Belgium, particularly the repair of household appliances, using a CGE model. They show that expansionary fiscal policies can be effective in encouraging the participation of households in circular-related activities. Restrictive fiscal policies can be an effective tool in reducing linear activities. Another strand of the literature emphasizes the existing trade-off between

FIGURE 1 CIRCEE (CIRCular Energy-Economy model) graphical representation.

repairing and purchasing new goods and its relevance for energy consumption and the longevity of goods in Japan (refer to Oguchi & Fuse, 2015, Nakamoto & Kagawa, 2018 and Nishijima et al., 2020).

Although the previous studies are interesting and innovative in their own way, they all focus on specific CE strategies without considering synergies and trade-offs that might arise between different CE strategies. As pointed out by Blomsma and Brennan (2017), it is necessary to assess and understand the simultaneous relationships that exist between different CE strategies. From our model results, we show that synergies may arise between different CE strategies, especially refuse, rethink, repair, and refurbish. In response to an increase in the EPR fee, consumers are not only incentivized to reduce their acquisition of new goods and to increase the repair of goods, but also, they are incentivized to engage in new consumption models such as sharing. Previous studies also neglect some industrial ecology concepts such as thermodynamic efficiency and mass balance. In addition, they do not emphasize enough the importance of heterogeneous households with different lifestyles, which is crucial as CE policies and new business models trigger new consumption behaviors. Pettifor et al. (2023) point out that shifting toward a low-carbon lifestyle involves modifying several aspects of one's daily routine and is largely driven by cognitive drivers, shaped by contextual factors. Exploring various lifestyle heterogeneity can also help us understand the differential response to public policy incentives.

Drawing on the existing literature of existing macroeconomic studies, and the 9R framework of Potting et al. (2017), we develop a stylized model, soft-linked to the IAM WITCH (Emmerling et al., 2016) and the LIFE model (Pettifor et al., 2023) to assess the environmental and economic impacts of CE strategies and new business models. The model includes microeconomic foundations, key industrial ecology concepts, and households' lifestyle heterogeneity. Andrews (2000) and Bruel et al. (2019) highlight the importance of microeconomic foundations in industrial ecology thinking to understand the decisions of economic agents and go beyond the product-oriented approach. The authors also point out the importance of incorporating social and behavioral parameters. The stylized model will serve as a starting point for the IAM community and help map CE strategies into existing climate scenarios. As an application, we assess the potential of EPR fees as a mean to trigger conscious consumption behaviors.

2 | METHODS

CIRCEE (CIRCular Energy-Economy model) is a deterministic dynamic and stochastic general equilibrium model with resource stock/flow consistency. It incorporates industrial ecology concepts to evaluate how CE strategies and enablers can decrease future GHG emissions and enhance resource efficiency. Figure 1 gives an overall picture of CIRCEE's industrial metabolism.¹

FIGURE 2 Consumption decisions in CIRCEE (CIRCular Energy-Economy model). Households consume energy services, semi-durable goods (e.g., furniture and clothing), and non-durable goods (e.g., food and packaging). Energy services are provided either by a sharing market or produced at home. Households produce at home energy services by owning durable goods and consuming energy. Also, households can decide to repair a part of their durable goods stock instead of buying conventional new durable goods to replace the old ones.

2.1 | Households

2.1.1 | Consumption decisions

Three heterogeneous households—low-carbon, cautious, and constrained households (refer to Section 2.2.1)—make intratemporal choices regarding the composition of their consumption basket and intertemporal choices between different types of assets—semidurable, durable, and capital goods—available to them to maximize their lifetime utility subject to a budget constraint (refer to Supporting Information A for a mathematical description). Households consume different types of goods, energy services, and circular services (see Figure 2). Energy services can be either home-produced from owning durable goods, such as cars or washing machines, and using energy or bought directly on a sharing market. Besides, owners of energy-using durable goods make their durable goods available for renting to other individuals when they are not in use.

Households have some habit persistence regarding consumption patterns, à la Hansen (1985). Habit persistence refers to the tendency of households to maintain their current consumption patterns over time; even if their environment changes, they resist changing their behavior over time. Various factors, such as social norms, personal preferences, or past experiences, can influence this behavior. This feature is important because some CE strategies modify the consumption habits of households. Also, households are heterogeneous in their lifestyles (see Section 3.1.3. below) and material context.

2.1.2 | Investments in assets

Households' investment decision and the user cost approach

Low-carbon and cautious households can invest in capital, durable, and semi-durable goods. Constrained households can invest in durable and semi-durable goods because they are constrained by their income and cannot save part of it. Durable goods in CIRCEE are energy-using durable goods. They include home appliances and cars, while semidurable goods include, among others, furniture and clothes. Semidurable and durable goods are considered assets as they can be used as collateral against future shocks by using the revenues from selling the goods. We use the Wicksellian user cost approach for semidurable and durable assets pricing as in Rust (1985). According to Diewert (2021), the asset price at a given time is better reflected by the user cost than by its acquisition price when a model includes the services provided by the good over its entire lifetime. Also, we include in the user cost the potential revenues from renting the durable good in the sharing market.

Households can repair a portion of their durable good stock. We assume that the imperfect substitution between repaired and newly produced durable goods occurs in the investment phase rather than in the production phase of the asset (refer to Supporting Information A.0.4). Rust (1985) points out that the hypothesis of perfect substitutability between used/repaired and new durable goods is strong as durable goods depreciate through time. Even though both products have the same function, they do not have the same quality. The decision between sharing, repairing, and

TABLE 1 Circular economy (CE) strategies in CIRCEE.

Bocken et al. (2016)	Potting et al. (2017)	Goal in CIRCEE_LIFE	Instruments in CIRCEE_LIFE
Narrowing the resource loop	R0: Refuse	Reduce consumption of energy-using durable goods and semidurable goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lifestyle changes • EPR fees • Import tariffs
	R1: Rethink	Sharing of energy-using durable goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lifestyle changes • Favorable taxation to sharing income • EPR fees
	R2: Reduce	Reduce the use of materials in goods and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shock on the material productivity • Waste tax • Material substitution
Slowing the resource loop	R4: Repair	Extending the life span instead of buying new energy-using durable goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lifestyle changes • Reduced consumption tax • Repair bonus • EPR fees
	R5: Refurbish	Extending the life span instead of buying new energy-using durable goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lifestyle changes • EPR fees • Reduced consumption tax
Closing the resource loop	R8: Recycle	Useful application of materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste tax • Subsidies to recycling firms • Price differential between primary and secondary materials

Abbreviation: EPR, extended producer responsibility.

buying new depends on price and technological effects. As in Benjaafar et al. (2019), owners of durable goods are the ones bearing the cost of ownership, but they can generate income from renting in a sharing market.

2.2 | CE strategies

CIRCEE can activate various CE policies to support the economy's transition toward circularity. Table 1 lists the six R strategies and the related policy instruments that can be activated in CIRCEE. Section A.8 of Supporting Information A lists in detail the implications of the instruments on the relevant equations. In this paper, as an illustration of the model's capabilities, we propose to focus on one particular policy, the EPR fees on durable goods (see Section 3.2.), under the presence of circular markets. Throughout the simulations, CE strategies other than EPR fees were not activated and are for future research.

2.2.1 | Behavioral aspects

We consider that each household has heterogeneous preferences for the consumption of different types of goods and services as a result of their lifestyle choices. The soft-linking of CIRCEE and LIFE model of (Pettifor et al., 2023) allows us to capture the mechanisms of lifestyle change (cognitions, behavior, and context).

Pettifor et al. (2023) have created a comprehensive typology of lifestyles across cognitive intentions toward low-carbon behaviors. Low-carbon behaviors are categorized following the avoid-shift-improve framework of van den Berg et al. (2019) and Creutzig et al. (2022) (refer to Table 2). The extent of engagement across A-S-I behaviors is shaped by social/material contextual indicators, including income and digital skills. Avoid' is driven by materially-challenged lifestyles. "Shift" and "Improve" are driven predominantly by low-carbon-driven lifestyle and are intentionally driven (environmental intentions and sufficiency), but they can also be driven by materially challenged lifestyles. For each lifestyle type, the authors have identified constraints restricting and enablers encouraging a low-carbon lifestyle.

In CIRCEE_LIFE model, the low-carbon lifestyle household is characterized by stronger low-carbon cognitions and enabling material and social contexts. The household is more likely to engage in a wide range of low-carbon behaviors. The cautious lifestyle household has weak cognitive drivers overall but noticeably high levels of perceived behavioral control, which relates to having moderate levels of wealth. Its lack of willingness to engage in a low-carbon lifestyle is also associated with its passive views on climate change. The constrained lifestyle household also has weak low-carbon cognitions and a less enabling material and social context. Despite its low environmental beliefs, its motivation to save money encourages them to adopt involuntary low-carbon lifestyles. Several authors have shown that lower-income households benefit and engage the most in the

TABLE 2 CIRCEE-LIFE and the avoid–shift–improve framework of Creutzig et al. (2022).

A-S-I	LIFE	CIRCEE
Avoid excess use and unsustainable consumption practices (reduce, repair, refuse)	Spend less on furniture, durable goods, clothing/engage in more sustainable and efficient purchase practices/engage in public/shared modes of transport	Reduce consumption of goods/share durable goods/repair and refurbish goods/intensify the use of long-lived products
Shift everyday activities (rethink)	Owens or uses “electrified” or “digitalized” goods and services	Share durable goods
Improve activities (refurbish, recycle)	Spends more on purchases related to maintenance and refurbishment	Spends more on purchases related to maintenance and refurbishment

sharing economy (refer to Chitnis et al., 2014, Fraiberger & Sundararajan, 2017, Grabs, 2015, Kim, 2019, Makov et al., 2020, and Meshulam et al., 2022).

2.3 | Sectors of production

2.3.1 | Materials-producing firms

The production of primary materials, which aggregate minerals, plastics, pulp and paper, wood, concrete, glass, ceramics, and fiber, is maintained at a high level of aggregation to capture the main transmission channels of CE strategies. In addition, a recycling firm produces secondary materials from a fixed proportion of recyclable waste supplied by the government at no cost. Both sectors produce from labor, capital, energy, and raw materials/waste.

Different sustainable waste management models are implemented globally to divert waste from landfills. The most used one is the EPR scheme based on the polluter-pays principle. In CIRCEE, the recycling firm receives subsidies from the government from the collection of EPR fees. EPR fees are assumed to be borne by households at the date of acquisition of products. Whether producers bear the cost and pass it on to the consumers or the consumers bear the cost has the same (tax) incidence in the model. If the producer bears the cost, it would be irrational for the firms not to pass on the extra EPR cost to consumers, except in cases of zero demand elasticity, where the tax incidence would not fall on consumers.

Prices of primary and secondary materials are considered exogenous and set on global markets. The quality differential between the materials is reflected by the substitution elasticity between primary and secondary materials.

2.3.2 | Final goods

The sectors produce from capital, labor, energy, and materials. The technology of production follows a standard constant elasticity substitution (CES) tree that combines intermediate CES nests (refer to Supporting Information A.1.2.1). They produce conventional nondurable, semidurable, durable, and capital goods. Restrictions in their production processes exist to incorporate some industrial ecology concepts (see Section 2.3.4. below).

2.3.3 | Circular-related services

The repair and sharing firms are competitors to new products firms as they divert buyers from purchasing new goods. The repair firm extends the longevity of a portion of the durable goods stock. Given the macro-structure of CIRCEE, the repaired good is assumed to be as good as new. The repair firm uses labor and capital inputs to produce repair services.

The sharing firm produces sharing services from durable goods, energy, and labor. It rents durable goods from households for a portion of the time they are not used in exchange for revenue. As it is standard in DSGE models, households own the capital stock of the economy and rent it out to firms on a rental market. We departed from this assumption to set up the sharing economy in CIRCEE. Households accumulate durable goods and decide to rent them on a rental market to the sharing firm. Also, they can use part of this durable good stock for their own utility. Analytically, whether the sharing firm owns the durable good stock or rents it out from households is mirrored in a general equilibrium setup. Besides, we assume that durable goods are homogeneous in their features and quality as in Benjaafar et al. (2019). We assume that the probability of matching sellers and renters is equal to 1, and no matching frictions exist given the long-run horizon of the model.

2.3.4 | Industrial ecology aspects

Pauliuk et al. (2017) emphasize the necessity of incorporating industrial ecology system linkages into IAMs. The authors highlight six areas for improvement: (i) global supply chains and life cycle perspective; (ii) linking capital services, stocks, and formation; (iii) material cycles; (iv) co-production, waste, and urban fabric; (v) physical balances and vintage tracking; and (vi) regional and processed detail. CIRCEE is soft-linked to the IAM WITCH and addresses some of these issues. First, CIRCEE has a macroeconomic closure budget, accounting for the environmental and industrial impacts of increasing technology demand in terms of resources. Second, CIRCEE links services to stocks, stocks to investments, and aggregate capital stock to material flows. While the capital stock is not in physical units (e.g., the number of machines), the material needed for a (monetary) unit of capital is tracked. Third, CIRCEE lacks a more disaggregated representation of different material cycles. Materials are for now aggregated in two materials—secondary and primary materials—and we do not look at different materials. Material flows are driven by the demand for consumption and investment goods, linking material processing activities to manufacturing, in-use stocks, waste management, and recycling. Material processing and recycling activities are physically linked to service needs, such as household energy services, allowing for the assessment of waste reduction strategies and refurbishing/repair activities. Fourth, CIRCEE includes a mass balance. Finally, CIRCEE is a stylized model not designed for detailed technological process representation but to understand the main macroeconomic transmission channels of CE strategies.

2.4 | Ensuring a realistic corridor for material productivity

For accounting reasons, the CES material nest that combines primary and secondary materials follows the work of van der Mensbrugghe and Peters (2016) to ensure that the mass balance condition is verified, and to track material flows in a more precise manner. Each new good sector obeys the rule of conservation of mass. The “volume-preserving” CES nest of material inputs becomes a combination of cost components rather than volume components, and the nest is optimized under the mass balance condition (see Section A.1.2. in Supporting Information A). As a robustness exercise, we found that keeping the standard CES function for the material nest does not verify the mass balance condition, while it does by following the “volume-preserving” CES function.

Also, to avoid excess dematerialization and excess materialization of the economy, the substitution elasticity between capital-labor-energy and materials in the production process of goods is constrained between]0, 1[. Having a substitution elasticity inferior to 1 rules out the possibility of having one input approaching or being equal to zero (see Supporting Information A.1.2.2). All inputs become essential in the production process of the good or the commodity. Early work from Dasgupta and Heal (1974) and Anderson (1987) advocated for a CES function with an elasticity of substitution strictly inferior to one.

In addition, to verify the thermodynamic efficiency condition that limits the transformation capacity of materials into goods, a material leakage parameter is attached to the material input, γ_{jt}^l .

The production process of each sector j follows the one of Skelton et al. (2020):

$$Y_{j,t} = \left[\alpha_j^{kle} (KLE_{j,t})^{\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} + \alpha_j^m \left((1 - \gamma_{j,t}^l) A_{j,t}^m M_{j,t} \right)^{\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma}{\sigma-1}} \quad (1)$$

where,

- $Y_{j,t}$ is the output;
- α_j^{kle} and α_j^m are distribution parameters;
- σ is the substitution elasticity;
- $\gamma_{j,t}^l$ is the material leakage parameter of the production process;
- $A_{j,t}^m$ is the material productivity;
- $M_{j,t}$ is aggregate material input.

The firm decides how much capital, labor, energy, and materials to use by maximizing profits under Equation (1). In addition to the profit maximization problem, we add another optimization problem that minimizes Equation (2) under the constraint of mass balance². It gives the amount of primary and secondary materials used in the production process. Additive material input $M_{j,t}^{add}$ is a volume-preserving CES function à la van der Mensbrugghe and Peters (2016) that minimizes the CES aggregation of material cost components under the constraint of material balance and is

equal to $(p_{j,t}^m \text{composite}^m M_{j,t}^m)$:

$$\min M_{j,t}^{\text{add}} = \left[\alpha_{j,t}^{\text{prim}} \left((\bar{p}_t^{\text{prim}} + (\tau_t^{\text{iw}}(1 - \omega_{\text{indus},t}^{\text{recycle}}) + \text{collection}_t) \gamma_{j,t}) M_{j,t}^{\text{prim}} \right)^{\frac{\sigma^m}{\sigma^m - 1}} + \alpha_{j,t}^{\text{sec}} \left((\bar{p}_t^{\text{sec}} + (\tau_t^{\text{iw}}(1 - \omega_{\text{indus},t}^{\text{recycle}}) + \text{collection}_t) \gamma_{j,t}) M_{j,t}^{\text{sec}} \right)^{\frac{\sigma^m}{\sigma^m - 1}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^m - 1}{\sigma^m}} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{s.t. } M_{j,t} = M_{j,t}^{\text{prim}} + M_{j,t}^{\text{secd}} \quad (3)$$

where,

- $\alpha_{j,t}^{\text{prim}}$ and $\alpha_{j,t}^{\text{sec}}$ are distribution parameters;
- \bar{p}_t^{prim} is the price of primary materials;
- τ_t^{iw} is the industrial waste tax;
- $\omega_{\text{indus},t}^{\text{landfill}}$ is the landfill rate of industrial waste;
- collection_t is the collection cost of waste;
- $\gamma_{j,t}$ is the material leakage parameter;
- \bar{p}_t^{sec} is the price of secondary materials;
- $M_{j,t}^{\text{prim}}$ and $M_{j,t}^{\text{secd}}$ are the primary and secondary material inputs;
- σ^m is the material substitution elasticity.

In addition to the minimization problem, we need to incorporate two different material prices, one that comes from the minimization problem $p_{j,t}^m \text{composite}^m$, and one that makes profits equal to zero $p_{j,t}^m$:

$$p_{j,t}^m \text{composite}^m = (1 - \gamma_{j,t}) A_{j,t}^m \left[(\alpha_{j,t}^{\text{prim}})^{1 - \sigma^m} (\bar{p}_t^{\text{prim}} + (\tau_t^{\text{iw}}(1 - \omega_{\text{indus},t}^{\text{recycle}}) + \text{collection}_t) \gamma_{j,t})^{-\sigma^m} + (\alpha_{j,t}^{\text{secd}})^{1 - \sigma^m} (\bar{p}_t^{\text{sec}} + (\tau_t^{\text{iw}}(1 - \omega_{\text{indus},t}^{\text{recycle}}) + \text{collection}_t) \gamma_{j,t})^{-\sigma^m} \right]^{-\frac{1}{\sigma^m}} \quad (4)$$

$$p_{j,t}^m = (p_{j,t}^m \text{composite}^m)^{\sigma^m} [(1 - \gamma_{j,t}) A_{j,t}^m]^{1 - \sigma^m} \left[(\alpha_{j,t}^{\text{prim}})^{1 - \sigma^m} (\bar{p}_t^{\text{prim}} + (\tau_t^{\text{iw}}(1 - \omega_{\text{indus},t}^{\text{recycle}}) + \text{collection}_t) \gamma_{j,t})^{1 - \sigma^m} + (\alpha_{j,t}^{\text{secd}})^{1 - \sigma^m} (\bar{p}_t^{\text{sec}} + (\tau_t^{\text{iw}}(1 - \omega_{\text{indus},t}^{\text{recycle}}) + \text{collection}_t) \gamma_{j,t})^{1 - \sigma^m} \right] \quad (5)$$

The average price of materials $p_{j,t}^m$ ensures that the following equation holds:

$$p_{j,t}^m M_{j,t} = (\bar{p}_t^{\text{prim}} + (\tau_t^{\text{iw}}(1 - \omega_{\text{indus},t}^{\text{recycle}}) + \text{collection}_t) \gamma_{j,t}) M_{j,t}^{\text{prim}} + (\bar{p}_t^{\text{secd}} + (\tau_t^{\text{iw}}(1 - \omega_{\text{indus},t}^{\text{recycle}}) + \text{collection}_t) \gamma_{j,t}) M_{j,t}^{\text{secd}} \quad (6)$$

To ensure that 100% recycling is not feasible, a "loss" parameter, calibrated from data from the Ministry of the Environment, is attached to the use of recyclable waste in the production process of secondary materials to capture the loss of materials during the recycling process.

2.5 | Resources stock and flows

The in-use stocks of the economy follow the work of Fishman et al. (2014). The in-use stock is composed only of storable goods as non-storable goods are consumed and disposed of immediately. As an example, the in-use stock for durable goods at the macro level follows:

$$\text{Materialstock}_{t+1}^{\text{durable}} = \text{Materialstock}_t^{\text{durable}} (1 - \delta_t^d) + (1 - \gamma_{\text{durable},t}) \left(\frac{M_{\text{durable},t}}{Y_{\text{durable},t}} \right) \left[Z_{\text{durable},t}^{\text{domestic}} + \text{materialintensity}_t^{\text{durable}} \text{IMP}_{\text{durable},t} \right] \quad (7)$$

where,

- $\text{Materialstock}_{t+1}^{\text{durable}}$ is the in-use stock of durable goods;
- δ_t^d is the depreciation rate of durable goods;

- $\gamma_{\text{durable},t}$ is the material loss during the production process of durable goods;
- $\frac{M_{\text{durable},t}}{Y_{\text{durable},t}}$ is the amount of material needs per unit of durable goods produced;
- $Z_{\text{durable},t}^{\text{domestic}}$ is the production of durable goods for domestic use;
- $\text{materialintensity}_t^{\text{durable}}$ is the material intensity of imports;
- $\text{IMP}_{\text{durable},t}$ is the imports of durable goods for domestic use.

Materials embedded in non-storable goods are accounted for in waste accumulation equations. Total waste is separated into municipal and industrial waste. Each source of waste is separated into landfills/incinerated waste and recyclable waste. As an example, landfilled/incinerated municipal waste at the macro-level follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Waste}_t^{\text{mun}} = & (1 - \omega_{\text{mun},t}^{\text{recycle}}) \left(\text{Materialstock}_t^{\text{durable}} \delta_t^d + \text{Materialstock}_t^{\text{semidurable}} \delta_t^{sd} \right. \\ & \left. + (1 - \gamma_{\text{nondurable},t}) \left(\frac{M_{\text{nondurable},t}}{Y_{\text{nondurable},t}} \right) \left[Z_{\text{nondurable},t}^{\text{domestic}} + \text{materialintensity}_t^{\text{nondurable}} \text{IMP}_{\text{nondurable},t} \right] \right) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where,

- $\text{Waste}_t^{\text{mun}}$ is municipal waste flows;
- $\omega_{\text{mun},t}^{\text{recycle}}$ is the share of recyclable waste in total waste.

2.6 | Trade

The incorporation of trade flows is important in the context of CE for two main reasons. First, while reducing the import of resources can benefit countries with limited resources, it may negatively impact resource-rich economies. Second, goods are produced with different material intensities in the world. The model can study scenarios where the domestic economy imposes special import tariffs on material-intensive imports to reduce its total domestic material consumption.

The domestic economy imports various goods and resources from the global market with Armington CES functions. To rule out trade frictions in the model, the trade block is built upon the law of one price such that the domestic/foreign economy cannot discriminate across markets in terms of prices. Also, we exclude the dynamics of exchange rates in the model because of the long-run horizon of the model.

Also, the recycling firm can import waste if its needs are higher than the total recyclable waste generated in the economy.

2.7 | Government

The government levies taxes, deploys CE policies, allocates public expenditures, and can activate redistribution mechanisms toward households. CE policies that can be implemented in CIRCEE are designed to foster sustainable consumption. The literature (among others, Douenne (2020), Antosiewicz et al. (2020), Douenne & Fabre (2020) and Corbier & Gonand (2024)) points out that climate mitigation policies can harm the economic welfare of households, especially the materially challenged households. Redistribution mechanisms are an important tool to attenuate the impact of such policies on households' economic welfare. It becomes increasingly crucial in the context of CIRCEE as there exist heterogeneous households with different liquidity constraints. CE policies can increase the final price of goods to foster sustainable consumption practices. To consider the possibility of harming households, we integrate into the modeling framework the possibility of activating a redistribution mechanism that redistributes the revenues from specific policies. For now, we assume that the revenues are redistributed equally to all households, though it would be interesting to also add a differentiated redistribution mechanism given the different liquidity constraints.

2.8 | Method statement

Given the high level of disaggregation of data in Japanese statistics and their availability, the model parameters are calibrated using Japanese national statistics (E-stat and the Agency of Natural Resources and Energy), the Japan Industrial Productivity Database 2021 from RIETI, literature review, the SSPs scenarios database, and expert consensus approaches. The material needs of each sector for the base year were computed in a combination of commodity price data from GLORIA database of Lenzen et al. (2017) and Lenzen et al. (2022), materials expenses from RIETI's input-output tables, waste generation data and Sankey Diagrams from the Ministry of the Environment, and DMC and trade data from Resource

TABLE 3 Variants for the extended producer responsibility (EPR) fee of energy-using durable goods in SSP2 and No_growth scenarios.

Variants	Annual increase	Share of the final price in 2018	Share of the final price in 2050
_currentpol	—	4.1%	4.1%
_4.5%	4.5%	4.1%	12.5%
_7%	7%	4.1%	22.5%

Panel's Global Material Flow database. For a more detailed description of the calibration methodology and parameter values, refer to Supporting Information B.

The paper assesses the environmental and economic impacts of increased EPR fees on energy-using durable goods in Japan. CE is essential for addressing climate change, improving resource security, and promoting economic growth in Japan, one of the least resource-rich OECD economies. Japan is vulnerable to material price fluctuations and supply security issues. To address these challenges, Japan has accelerated its transition toward a CE system, implementing policies such as the sound material-cycle society.

EPR fees for household appliances and cars in Japan are modest, ranging from 4400 JPY for a washing machine to 20,000 JPY for a car (Hotta et al., 2014 and Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry, nd). Increasing EPR fees or implementing eco-modulation is crucial for promoting green product design and conscious consumption (Dalhammar et al., 2021, Hogg et al., 2020, Laubinger et al., 2021, Lifset et al., 2023, Micheaux & Aggeri, 2021).

Two no-policy scenarios, *SSP2_{ef}* and *Nogrowth_{ef}*, and two policy scenarios for EPR fee evolution under repairing and sharing markets are considered (refer to Table 3). Other CE strategies in Table 1 are not activated in the scenarios. *Nogrowth_{ef}* assumes no economic growth in Japan. In CIRCEE, EPR fees are included as a share of the final product price. The high scenario considers increasing the EPR fee from 4.1% to 22.5% of the final price, as suggested by Micheaux and Aggeri (2021) and Hogg et al. (2020) for batteries and electrical and electronic equipment (EEE).

3 | RESULTS

In response to the increase in the EPR fee, households face a trade-off between repairing parts of their old stock of durable goods, engaging in the sharing economy, and acquiring new durable goods. All three types of households react positively to the economic incentives and engage in conscious consumption activities by decreasing their durable goods acquisitions in the long run (see graphs (a)–(c) of Figure 3) and substituting toward circular services, such as repairing and sharing (see graphs (d)–(i) of Figure 3). Increasing the EPR fee on energy-using durable goods effectively decreases the acquisition of new energy-using durable goods compared to the no-policy variant. Compared to the SSP2 scenario, the Nogrowth scenario gives the most favorable outcomes.

In addition, a higher demand for energy services consumed from sharing infrastructures increases the intensity of the use of durable goods, which further decreases the need to acquire new durable goods. Also, households substitute for nondurable goods consumption in the long run. In the policy variants, nondurable good consumption is approximately 0.1% higher compared to the no-policy variant. Compared to the no policy variant, the lower acquisition of durable goods in the long run, and hence the lower consumption of energy services at home by households, decreases relatively more the amount of energy that households consume in the policy variants (see graph (a) of Figure 5).

The “constrained” household, which is more contextually driven, in absolute levels, substitutes relatively more toward circular services in response to the policy incentive compared to other households because of the liquidity constraints it is facing (see graphs (g) and (i) of Figure 3). Engaging in repairing services and sharing services is seen as a more cost-effective alternative for the household.

Until 2037, households are likely to consume more shared energy services than home-produced ones under the current policy scenario, though the differences from alternative policy scenarios are minor (see graphs (g)–(i) of Figure 3). Anticipating higher EPR fees in the future in the alternative policy scenarios, households will initially buy more durable goods and consume relatively more energy services at home in the short- to medium-run (see graphs (a)–(c) of 3) but reduce purchases later as the negative price effects of EPR fees on the acquisition of durable goods outweighs the energy efficiency gains effect on the price of energy services consumed at home after 2037. This leads households to consume fewer shared services in a current policy scenario compared to policy scenarios.

The decrease in new durable goods acquisition reduces households' net additions to the in-use stock of durable goods (see graph (b) of Figure 4); hence, municipal waste is lower in the policy variants compared to the no-policy variant (see graph (a) of Figure 4). The differences between the no policy variant and the policy variants are not high because nondurable goods (e.g., packaging waste) and semidurable goods (kitchen utensils, glass, clothing, and furniture waste) represent the majority of municipal waste in Japan. According to the Ministry of the Environment, Japan (2019), food waste, packaging, glass textiles, and plastics represent approximately 65% of total municipal waste, while metals represent approximately 10% in 2018. Additionally, it is important to consider that the effects of the policy on waste reduction will become apparent only after several years, as durable goods have long-lived products.

FIGURE 3 Evolution of consumption variables compared to 2020, for the no-policy variant ($_currentpol$) and the two policy variants ($_4.5\%$ and $_7\%$). Nogrowth and SSP2 are the two variants of economic growth in Japan - Source: CIRCEE_LIFE. The underlying data for this figure are available in Results_xlsx in [Supporting Information](#).

On the production side, the lower demand for new durable goods results in lower material and energy needs for producing durable goods compared to the no-policy variant (see graph (e) of Figure 4 and graph (b) of Figure 5). Substituting for sharing services, however, increases the energy used by the sharing sector for the production of these services, which partially offsets the decrease in energy consumption. Also, the energy needed to produce the materials is lower in the policy variants than in the no-policy variant. However, the differences are insignificant because durable goods represent approximately 2.5% of the total material needs of Japan in 2018. Machinery, equipment, and housing production sectors make the most of the material needs. Despite a lower energy demand from households and the durable good producing firm, in response to a higher demand, the sharing firm and marginally the nondurable good firm drive up the total final energy demand of the economy (see graph (c) of Figure 5). Nondurable goods make up approximately 85% of Japan's total consumption, representing approximately 60% of the total energy needs of the economy. The decrease in final energy demand in the two scenarios is mainly driven by the increase in energy efficiency in all variants. The effect on CO₂ emissions is not significant because of the substitution mechanisms put in place by households in response to the policy (see graph (d) of Figure 5).

Total imports of raw materials and primary and secondary materials are lower in the policy variants compared to the no-policy variant (see graph (d) of Figure 4). Total imports of raw materials are the lowest for the highest increase of the EPR fee, improving material resource security in Japan.

4 | DISCUSSION

4.1 | Policy implications

Consumer choices are important for the success of EPR fees. From the model's results, fees will increase the saliency of the need for environmental consumption, making consumers more aware of the consequences of their choices. As a result of a higher price for durable goods, households are substituting for circular services, which reduces material and energy requirements for the production of these goods. Although an increase in EPR fees leads to a reduction in net additions to durable goods in-use stocks, their impact on waste generation is mitigated by adapting consumption practices. As a response to the policy, households may shift their consumption toward goods that consume more materials and energy during production, such as nondurable goods, which undermines the initial positive effects of fees on the reduction of total waste generation and

FIGURE 4 Evolution of material in-use stock and flows and waste flows in million metric ton compared to 2020, for the no-policy variant (*_currentpol*) and the two policy variants (*_4.5%* and *_7%*). NoGrowth and SSP2 are the two variants of economic growth in Japan. Source: CIRCEE_LIFE simulations. The underlying data for this figure are available in Results_xlsx in [Supporting Information](#).

energy consumption. In addition, a shift toward sharing services increases the energy needed to produce sharing services, which partially offsets the reduction in households' energy consumption as a consequence of the policy. In the literature, Brusselaers et al. (2022) find similar results where they show that expansionary fiscal policies can be effective in encouraging the participation of households in circular-related activities.

In addition, from the model's results, the most significant effects of the alternative policy scenarios are observed in the NoGrowth scenarios. In contrast, the SSP2 scenarios result in relatively minor impacts on environmental outcomes. This underscores a potential trade-off between economic growth and environmental objectives.

As a result, when adopting such policies, it is important to remain aware of consumer-driven substitution mechanisms that may affect the intended benefits for resource use, waste production, and CO₂ emissions. While the policy may help the economy to slow the resource loop for certain products, its effect on CO₂ emissions might be negligible or even adverse if it encourages a shift toward the sharing economy that can result in an increased usage rate of durable goods and potential rebound effects. Also, another mechanism through which rebound effects unfold in CIRCEE is through substitution mechanisms. When faced with a higher EPR fee, these substitution mechanisms can cause an increase in the consumption of goods that are not subject to EPR fees. At the aggregate level, these goods may actually require more resources during their production

FIGURE 5 Evolution of energy use in EJ and CO₂ emissions in Mt CO₂, for the no-policy variant (*_currentpol*) and the two policy variants (.4.5% and .7%). Nogrowth and SSP2 are the two variants of economic growth in Japan. Source: CIRCEE_LIFE simulations. The underlying data for this figure are available in Results_xlsx in [Supporting Information](#).

process, thereby triggering a rebound effect on overall resource use. Zink and Geyer (2017) emphasize that circular economy activities can enhance economic production, potentially leading to rebound effects that mitigate the initial advantages of these activities.

It is important to acknowledge that EPR schemes also exist for other categories of goods, such as semidurable and nondurable items, including packaging and furniture. If the model were to simultaneously incorporate EPR schemes across these various categories, the resulting consumer behavior changes could lead to a broader shift in consumption patterns, potentially leading to a reduction in consumption levels and energy levels at the aggregate level. This suggests that an integrated approach to EPR implementation could play a significant role in driving sustainable consumer choices.

The outcomes are contingent on the specific structure and parameters of the model. In the case of CIRCEE, on the consumer side, the most influential parameters are the substitution elasticities which, as with all macroeconomic models, drive the model's dynamics. Consumption choices depend on the range values of these elasticities. There is a need for more comprehensive data on the sharing economy and repair activities to accurately estimate the substitution elasticities that influence consumption behaviors. Moreover, many countries either do not track or only partially track sharing economy data, which remain challenging to quantify and define. Until such data are widely accessible, models must rely on arbitrary range values for these crucial parameters.

4.2 | Limitations and future research

The current version of CIRCEE does not account for endogenous green product design, so whether the EPR fee incentivizes producers to engage in green product design is not considered. While behavioral plasticities can enable many CE strategies, they rely on design technology aimed at extending product lifespans. Future CIRCEE versions will incorporate these aspects. Additionally, studying firms' pricing strategies related to green product design would be interesting (refer to Abbey et al. (2015), Abbey et al. (2015), Nishijima et al. (2020), Oh (2019), Razeghian and Weber (2019a), and Razeghian & Weber (2019b)). Model results show that higher EPR fees can modify consumer habits toward increased repair and longevity of durable goods. Producers, recognizing potential decreases in turnover and the presence of a sharing market, might design more durable products with a premium to incentivize new purchases. A detailed life-cycle assessment for specific products, requiring extensive research and data collection on new green design technologies and cost implications, is necessary. This would necessitate a disaggregated

product representation in CIRCEE, focusing on reparability and durability, and could involve linking product-focused industrial ecology models with CIRCEE.

Incorporating endogenous technological advancements to increase material productivity and recycling quality depends on comprehensive and detailed data. Endogenous representation of technical change for material productivity and recycling quality in macroeconomic models is still scarce. Patents can reveal innovation directions and future market trends regarding material productivity and recycling technologies. This requires open data on patents and/or R&D investments, along with in-depth industrial surveys to assess the availability, cost, and efficacy of recycling technologies.

Understanding the dynamics between primary and secondary markets is equally important. Clarifying how these markets interact will help assess how technological changes affect recycling behaviors.

The advancement of CIRCEE depends on open access to datasets and sufficient funding to study CE's multifaceted aspects, from micro-level green product design specifics to macro-level resource efficiency and economic growth implications. Securing dedicated funding is critical for extensive data collection. As an open-source model, CIRCEE can benefit from research community support, fostering collaborative development through shared knowledge and resources. Such a model would provide policymakers with valuable insights, enabling well-informed decisions that balance the synergies and trade-offs of CE strategies.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101056868 (CIR-COMOD) and No. 101081604 (PRISMA), and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 870245 (GEOCEP).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon request.

ORCID

Darius Corbier <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5342-1974>

Laurent Drouet <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4087-7662>

ENDNOTES

¹ In the current version of CIRCEE, we abstract from the extraction behavior of mining and quarrying industries. Given that the national economy is viewed as resource-poor, CIRCEE treats raw material imports as equivalent to the total of imports and domestic extraction reported in national resource statistics.

² CIRCEE complies with total mass balance at the aggregate level: all material flows entering the economy equal outputs of waste and emissions, minus stock changes.

REFERENCES

- Abbey, J. D., Blackburn, J. D., & Guide Jr, V. D. R. (2015). Optimal pricing for new and remanufactured products. *Journal of Operations Management*, 36, 130–146.
- Abbey, J. D., Meloy, M. G., Guide Jr, V. D. R., & Atalay, S. (2015). Remanufactured products in closed-loop supply chains for consumer goods. *Production and Operations Management*, 24(3), 488–503.
- Aguilar Esteva, L. C., Kasliwal, A., Kinzler, M. S., Kim, H. C., & Keoleian, G. A. (2021). Circular economy framework for automobiles: Closing energy and material loops. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 25(4), 877–889.
- Akimoto, K., & Futagami, K. (2018). Transition from a linear economy toward a circular economy in the Ramsey model (Technical Report). Graduate School of Economics, Osaka University, Japan.
- Anderson, C. L. (1987). The production process: Inputs and wastes. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 14(1), 1–12.
- Andrews, C. J. (2000). Building a micro foundation for industrial ecology. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 4(3), 35–51.
- Antosiewicz, M., Nikas, A., Szpor, A., Witajewski-Baltvilks, J., & Doukas, H. (2020). Pathways for the transition of the polish power sector and associated risks. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 35, 271–291.
- Argentiero, A., D'Amato, A., & Zoli, M. (2022). Waste recycling policies and Covid-19 pandemic in an E-DSGE model. *Waste Management*, 141, 290–299.
- Benjaafar, S., Kong, G., Li, X., & Courcoubetis, C. (2019). Peer-to-peer product sharing: Implications for ownership, usage, and social welfare in the sharing economy. *Management Science*, 65(2), 477–493.
- Blomsma, F., & Brennan, G. (2017). The emergence of circular economy: a new framing around prolonging resource productivity. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 21(3), 603–614.
- Bongers, A., & Casas, P. (2022). The circular economy and the optimal recycling rate: A macroeconomic approach. *Ecological Economics*, 199, 107504.
- Bruel, A., Kronenberg, J., Troussier, N., & Guillaume, B. (2019). Linking industrial ecology and ecological economics: A theoretical and empirical foundation for the circular economy. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 23(1), 12–21.
- Brusselaers, J., Breemersch, K., Geerken, T., Christis, M., Lahcen, B., & Dams, Y. (2022). Macroeconomic and environmental consequences of circular economy measures in a small open economy. *The Annals of Regional Science*, 68, 283–306.

- Chauhan, C., Parida, V., & Dhir, A. (2022). Linking circular economy and digitalisation technologies: A systematic literature review of past achievements and future promises. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 177, 121508.
- Chitnis, M., Sorrell, S., Druckman, A., Firth, S. K., & Jackson, T. (2014). Who rebounds most? Estimating direct and indirect rebound effects for different UK socioeconomic groups. *Ecological Economics*, 106, 12–32.
- Corbier, D., & Gonand, F. (2024). A hybrid electricity-economy model to assess the aggregate impacts of low-carbon transition: An application to France. *Ecological Economics*, 216, 108027.
- Couix, Q. (2019). Natural resources in the theory of production: The Georgescu-Roegen/daly versus Solow/Stiglitz controversy. *The European Journal of the History of Economic Thought*, 26(6), 1341–1378.
- Creutzig, F., Niamir, L., Bai, X., Callaghan, M., Cullen, J., Díaz-José, J., Figueroa, M., Grubler, A., Lamb, W. F., Leip, A., & Masanet, E. (2022). Demand-side solutions to climate change mitigation consistent with high levels of well-being. *Nature Climate Change*, 12(1), 36–46.
- Dalhammar, C., Wihlborg, E., Milios, L., Richter, J. L., Svensson-Höglund, S., Russell, J., & Thidell, Å. (2021). Enabling reuse in extended producer responsibility schemes for white goods: Legal and organisational conditions for connecting resource flows and actors. *Circular Economy and Sustainability*, 1(2), 671–695.
- Dasgupta, P., & Heal, G. (1974). The optimal depletion of exhaustible resources. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 41(5), 3–28.
- de Oliveira, C. T., & Oliveira, G. G. A. (2023). What circular economy indicators really measure? An overview of circular economy principles and sustainable development goals. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 190, 106850.
- Diewert, W. E. (2021). Consumer price index theory. https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2021-05/Session_3_Diewert_Paper%20.pdf
- Douenne, T. (2020). The vertical and horizontal distributive effects of energy taxes: A case study of a French policy. *The Energy Journal*, 41(3), 231–254.
- Douenne, T., & Fabre, A. (2020). French attitudes on climate change, carbon taxation and other climate policies. *Ecological Economics*, 169, 106496.
- Emmerling, J., Drouet, L., Reis, L., Bevione, M., Berger, L., Bosetti, V., Carrara, S., De Cian, E., De Maere D'Aertrycke, G., Longden, T., & Malpede, M. (2016). The witch 2016 model-documentation and implementation of the shared socioeconomic pathways. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2800970
- Fishman, T., Schandl, H., Tanikawa, H., Walker, P., & Krausmann, F. (2014). Accounting for the material stock of nations. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 18(3), 407–420.
- Fraiberger, S. P., & Sundararajan, A. (2017). Peer-to-peer rental markets in the sharing economy (Research Paper). NYU Stern School of Business.
- Gaustad, G., Krystofik, M., Bustamante, M., & Badami, K. (2018). Circular economy strategies for mitigating critical material supply issues. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 135, 24–33.
- Germain, M. (2019). Georgescu-Roegen versus Solow/Stiglitz: Back to a controversy. *Ecological Economics*, 160, 168–182.
- Grabs, J. (2015). The rebound effects of switching to vegetarianism. A microeconomic analysis of Swedish consumption behavior. *Ecological Economics*, 116, 270–279.
- Grüning, P., Banionienė, J., Dagilienė, L., Donadelli, M., Jüppner, M., Kizys, R., & Lessmann, K. (2021). The quadrilemma of a small open circular economy through a prism of the 9r strategies (Technical Report). Bank of Lithuania.
- Hansen, G. D. (1985). Indivisible labor and the business cycle. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 16(3), 309–327.
- Hartley, K., van Santen, R., & Kirchherr, J. (2020). Policies for transitioning towards a circular economy: Expectations from the European Union (EU). *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 155, 104634.
- Hogg, D., Sherrington, C., Papineschi, J., Hilton, M., Massie, A., & Jones, P. (2020). Study to support preparation of the commission's guidance for extended producer responsibility schemes (Report for DG Environment of the European Commission). *Eunomia*.
- Hotta, Y., Santo, A., & Tasaki, T. (2014). EPR-based electronic home appliance recycling system under home appliance recycling act of Japan (Discussion Paper). Institute of Global Environmental Strategies. <https://www.iges.or.jp/en/pub/epr-based-electronic-home-appliance-recycling/en>
- IPCC. (2023). Climate change 2022: Mitigation of climate change, Working Group III contribution to the sixth assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.
- Kim, M. J. (2019). Benefits and concerns of the sharing economy: economic analysis and policy implications. *KDI Journal of Economic Policy*, 41(1), 15–41.
- Kinnaman, T., & Yokoo, H.-F. (2011). The environmental consequences of global reuse. *American Economic Review*, 101(3), 71–76.
- Korhonen, J., Honkasalo, A., & Seppälä, J. (2018). Circular economy: the concept and its limitations. *Ecological Economics*, 143, 37–46.
- Lafforgue, G., & Rouge, L. (2019). A dynamic model of recycling with endogenous technological breakthrough. *Resource and Energy Economics*, 57, 101–118.
- Lahcen, B., Eyckmans, J., Rousseau, S., Dams, Y., & Brusselselaers, J. (2022). Modelling the circular economy: Introducing a supply chain equilibrium approach. *Ecological Economics*, 197, 107451.
- Laubinger, F., Brown, A., Dubois, M., & Börkey, P. (2021). Modulated fees for extended producer responsibility schemes (EPR). https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/modulated-fees-for-extended-producer-responsibility-schemes-epr_2a42f54b-en.html
- Lee, K., & Cha, J. (2020). Towards improved circular economy and resource security in South Korea. *Sustainability*, 13(1), 17.
- Leipold, S., Petit-Boix, A., Luo, A., Helander, H., Simoens, M., Ashton, W. S., Babbitt, C. W., Bala, A., Bening, C. R., Birkved, M., & Blomsma, F. (2023). Lessons, narratives, and research directions for a sustainable circular economy. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 27(1), 6–18.
- Lenzen, M., Geschke, A., Abd Rahman, M. D., Xiao, Y., Fry, J., Reyes, R., Dietzenbacher, E., Inomata, S., Kanemoto, K., Los, B., & Moran, D. (2017). The Global MRIO Lab—charting the world economy. *Economic Systems Research*, 29(2), 158–186.
- Lenzen, M., Geschke, A., West, J., Fry, J., Malik, A., Giljum, S., Milà i Canals, L., Piñero, P., Lutter, S., Wiedmann, T., & Li, M. (2022). Implementing the material footprint to measure progress towards sustainable development goals 8 and 12. *Nature Sustainability*, 5(2), 157–166.
- Lifset, R., Kalimo, H., Jukka, A., Kautto, P., & Miettinen, M. (2023). Restoring the incentives for eco-design in extended producer responsibility: The challenges for eco-modulation. *Waste Management*, 168, 189–201.
- Lu, Y., Schandl, H., Wang, H., & Zhu, J. (2024). China's pathway towards a net zero and circular economy: A model-based scenario analysis. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 204, 107514.
- Makov, T., Shepon, A., Krones, J., Gupta, C., & Chertow, M. (2020). Social and environmental analysis of food waste abatement via the peer-to-peer sharing economy. *Nature Communications*, 11(1), 1156.
- Markevych, K., Maistro, S., Koval, V., & Paliukh, V. (2022). Mining sustainability and circular economy in the context of economic security in Ukraine. *Mining of Mineral Deposits*, 16(1), 101–113.
- Masui, T. (2005). Policy evaluations under environmental constraints using a computable general equilibrium model. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 166(3), 843–855.

- McCarthy, A., Dellink, R., & Bibas, R. (2018). The macroeconomics of the circular economy transition: A critical review of modelling approaches. https://stag-circular.eesc.europa.eu/platform/sites/default/files/knowledge_-_oecd_ce_transition.pdf
- Meshulam, T., Font-Vivanco, D., Blass, V., & Makov, T. (2022). Sharing economy rebound: The case of peer-to-peer sharing of food waste. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 27(3), 882–895.
- Micheaux, H., & Aggeri, F. (2021). Eco-modulation as a driver for eco-design: A dynamic view of the French collective EPR scheme. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 289, 125714.
- Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry. (n.d.). Automobile recycling fee. https://www.meti.go.jp/policy/mono_info_service/mono/automobile/automobile_recycle/other/pdf/pamphlet/foreigner.pdf
- Ministry of the Environment, Japan. (2019). Results of the general waste disposal business reality survey (fiscal year 2018). <https://www.env.go.jp/content/900515308.pdf>
- Nakamoto, Y., & Kagawa, S. (2018). Role of vehicle inspection policy in climate mitigation: The case of Japan. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 224, 87–96.
- Nechifor, V., Calzadilla, A., Bleischwitz, R., Winning, M., Tian, X., & Usubiaga, A. (2020). Steel in a circular economy: Global implications of a green shift in china. *World Development*, 127, 104775.
- Nishijima, D., Nansai, K., Kagawa, S., & Oguchi, M. (2020). Conflicting consequences of price-induced product lifetime extension in circular economy: The impact on metals, greenhouse gas, and sales of air conditioners. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 162, 105023.
- Oguchi, M., & Fuse, M. (2015). Regional and longitudinal estimation of product lifespan distribution: A case study for automobiles and a simplified estimation method. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 49(3), 1738–1743.
- Oh, H. (2019). The role of durables replacement and second-hand markets in a business-cycle model. *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking*, 51(4), 761–786.
- Okushima, S., & Yamashita, H. (2005). A general equilibrium analysis of waste management policy in Japan. *Hitotsubashi Journal of Economics*, 46(1), 111–134.
- Ordóñez-de Haro, J. M., & Torres, J. L. (2019). Sharing economy in macroeconomics: Collaborative consumption and durable goods (Technical Report).
- Parajuly, K., Fitzpatrick, C., Muldoon, O., & Kuehr, R. (2020). Behavioral response for the circular economy: A review with focus on electronic waste management in the eu. *Resources, Conservation & Recycling: X*, 6, 100035.
- Pauliuk, S., Arvesen, A., Stadler, K., & Hertwich, E. G. (2017). Industrial ecology in integrated assessment models. *Nature Climate Change*, 7(1), 13–20.
- Pauliuk, S., Fishman, T., Heeren, N., Berrill, P., Tu, Q., Wolfram, P., & Hertwich, E. G. (2021). Linking service provision to material cycles: A new framework for studying the resource efficiency–climate change (RECC) nexus. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 25(2), 260–273.
- Pettifor, H., Agnew, M., & Wilson, C. (2023). A framework for measuring and modelling low-carbon lifestyles. *Global Environmental Change*, 82, 102739.
- Pittl, K., Amigues, J.-P., & Kuhn, T. (2010). Recycling under a material balance constraint. *Resource and Energy Economics*, 32(3), 379–394.
- Potting, J., Hekkert, M. P., Worrell, E., & Hanemaaijer, A. (2017). Circular economy: Measuring innovation in the product chain. *Planbureau voor de Leefomgeving*, (2544).
- Razeghian, M., & Weber, T. A. (2019a). The advent of the sharing culture and its effect on product pricing. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 33, 100801.
- Razeghian, M., & Weber, T. A. (2019b). Strategic durability with sharing markets. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 19, 79–96.
- Rust, J. (1985). Stationary equilibrium in a market for durable assets. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*, 53(4), 783–805.
- Schroeder, P., Anggraeni, K., & Weber, U. (2019). The relevance of circular economy practices to the sustainable development goals. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 23(1), 77–95.
- Serrano, T., Aparcana, S., Bakhtiari, F., & Laurent, A. (2021). Contribution of circular economy strategies to climate change mitigation: Generic assessment methodology with focus on developing countries. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 25(6), 1382–1397.
- Shevchenko, T., Saidani, M., Ranjbari, M., Kronenberg, J., Danko, Y., & Laitala, K. (2023). Consumer behavior in the circular economy: Developing a product-centric framework. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 384, 135568.
- Skelton, A. C., Paroussos, L., & Allwood, J. M. (2020). Comparing energy and material efficiency rebound effects: An exploration of scenarios in the gem-e3 macroeconomic model. *Ecological Economics*, 173, 106544.
- Szilagy, A., Cioca, L.-I., Bacali, L., Lakatos, E.-S., & Birgovan, A.-L. (2022). Consumers in the circular economy: A path analysis of the underlying factors of purchasing behaviour. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(18), 11333.
- Takimoto, H., Kosai, S., Watari, T., & Yamasue, E. (2024). Circular economy can mitigate rising mining demand from global vehicle electrification. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 209, 107748.
- van den Berg, N. J., Hof, A. F., Akenji, L., Edelenbosch, O. Y., van Sluisveld, M. A., Timmer, V. J., & van Vuuren, D. P. (2019). Improved modelling of lifestyle changes in integrated assessment models: Cross-disciplinary insights from methodologies and theories. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 26, 100420.
- van der Laan, A. Z., & Aurisicchio, M. (2020). A framework to use product-service systems as plans to produce closed-loop resource flows. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 252, 119733.
- van der Mensbrugghe, D., & Peters, J. C. (2016). Volume preserving CES and CET formulations. https://www.gtap.agecon.purdue.edu/resources/res_display.asp?RecordID=5070
- Yokoo, H.-F., & Kinnaman, T. C. (2013). Global reuse and optimal waste policy. *Environment and Development Economics*, 18(5), 595–614.
- Zhou, S., & Smulders, S. (2021). Closing the loop in a circular economy: Saving resources or suffocating innovations?. *European Economic Review*, 139, 103857.
- Zink, T., & Geyer, R. (2017). Circular economy rebound. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 21(3), 593–602.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

How to cite this article: Corbier, D., Pettifor, H., Agnew, M., & Drouet, L. (2024). CIRCEE, the CIRcular Energy Economy model: Bridging the gap between economic and industrial ecology concepts. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13587>

Appendix A Model's analytical description

A.0.1 Low-carbon and cautious households

Low-carbon and cautious lifestyle households maximize intertemporally their utility function by choosing the optimal composition of their consumption basket and their asset portfolio subject to a budget constraint. Households maximize the following Constant Relative Risk Aversion (CRRA) utility function à la [1] for both types of households i , where $i \in (lowcarbon, cautious)$, under budget constraints as follows:

$$\max \beta \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{(C_{i,t} - h_{i,t}C_{i,t-1})^{1-\sigma^{ies}} - 1}{1 - \sigma^{ies}} \quad (A1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{s.t. } & (1 + \tau^{vat}) \left[p_{nd,t}ND_{i,t} + p_{sd,t}Inv_{i,t}^{semidurable} + p_{d,t}(Inv_{i,t}^{\tilde{newdurable}} + Inv_{i,t}^{newdurable}) \right. \\ & \left. + p_{share,t}ES_{i,t}^{sharing} + (p_{h,t}^{el} + \tau_{h,t}^{el})El_{i,t} + (p_{h,t}^{nel} + \tau_{h,t}^{nel})Nel_{i,t} \right] \\ & + p_{d,t}fee_{durable,t}^{ep}r(Inv_{i,t}^{\tilde{newdurable}} + Inv_{i,t}^{newdurable}) + fee_{semidurable,t}^{ep}rInv_{i,t}^{semidurable} \\ & + \tau_t^{deposit}(1 - \omega_{mun,t}^{recycle}) \left[\frac{M_{nondurable,t}}{Y_{nondurable,t}} (Z_{nondurable,t}^{domestic} + materialintensity_t^{nondurable} \right. \\ & \left. IMP_{nondurable,t}) \frac{ND_{i,t}}{ND_t} + Materialstock_t^{semidurable} \delta_t^{sd} \frac{SD_{i,t}}{SD_t} \right] + p_{k,t}Inv_{i,t}^{capital} \\ & + p_{repair,t}(1 + \tau_t^{vatreduced})(1 - bonus_t^{durable})Inv_{i,t}^{repair,durable} \\ & = (1 - \tau^l)w_tL_{i,t} + r_{i,t}^d(1 - fee_t^{platform})(1 - \tau_t^{sharing})(1 - u_t)\mu_tD_{i,t} \\ & + (1 - \tau^k)(1 - \delta^k)r_tK_{i,t} + TR_t + PS_{i,t} + TB_{i,t} + Carbon_{i,t}^{redis} + EPR_{i,t}^{redis} \end{aligned} \quad (A2)$$

where,

- β is the discount factor
- $C_{i,t}$ is the aggregate consumption basket
- $h_{i,t}$ is a habit persistence parameter
- α^c is a distribution parameter
- σ^{ies} is the intertemporal elasticity of substitution
- $(ND_{i,t}, ES_{i,t}^{sharing})$ are the non-durable good and sharing services consumption
- $(p_{nd,t}, p_{sd,t}, p_{d,t}, p_{share,t}, p_{repair,t}, p_{k,t})$ are the aggregate price of non-durable good, semi-durable good, durable goods, sharing services, repairing services, capital goods (numeraire of the model)
- $(fee_{durable,t}^{ep}r, fee_{semidurable,t}^{ep}r)$ are the EPR fees charged to consumers for the acquisition of energy-using durable goods and semi-durables
- $(Inv_{i,t}^{semidurable}, Inv_{i,t}^{capital}, Inv_{i,t}^{\tilde{newdurable}}, Inv_{i,t}^{newdurable})$ are the investments in semi-durable goods and new durable goods
- $bonus_t^{durable}$ are the bonus on repairing services
- $(p_{h,t}^{el}, p_{h,t}^{nel})$ are the retail prices of electricity and fuels
- $(\tau_{h,t}^{el}, \tau_{h,t}^{nel})$ are the electricity and fuel tax
- $(El_{i,t}, Nel_{i,t})$ are the electricity and fuel consumption
- $\tau_t^{deposit}$ is the volume-based deposit waste fee
- $\omega_{mun,t}^{recycle}$ is the share of municipal waste that is recyclable
- (ND_t, SD_t, D_t) are the total domestic consumption of non-durable, semi-durable good stock and durable good stock
- $\gamma_{nondurable,t}$ is the material leakage during the production process of non-durable goods (i.e. industrial waste)
- $M_{nondurable,t}$ is the aggregate material inputs of the non-durable firms
- $Y_{nondurable,t}$ is the domestic production of non-durable goods
- $(Z_{nondurable,t}^{domestic}, IMP_{nondurable,t})$ are the domestic demand and imports of domestically produced non-durable goods
- $(materialintensity_t^{nondurable}, materialintensity_t^{semidurable}, materialintensity_t^{durable})$ are the material intensities of imported non-durable goods, semi-durable goods, and durable goods. It is the materials embedded in trade.
- $(\delta_t^{sd}, \delta_{i,t}^d, \delta_t^k)$ are the depreciation rates of semi-durable, durable and capital goods
- $(Materialstock_t^{semidurable}, Materialstock_t^{durable})$ are the in-use stock of semi-durable and durable goods
- $(\tau_t^{vat}, \tau_t^{vatreduced}, \tau^l, \tau_t^{sharing}, \tau^k)$ are the consumption tax, the reduced consumption tax on repair services, the labor tax, the sharing income tax, and the capital income tax
- $Inv_{i,t}^{repair,durable}$ are the durable goods and capital goods being repaired
- w_t is nominal wages

- $L_{i,t}$ is the total number of hours worked
- $r_{i,t}^d$ is the rental rate of durable goods in the sharing market. The study of rental income derived from sharing durable goods in a peer-to-peer market holds significance as it can help offset the expensive nature of owning such goods. [2] emphasizes that this income can make the ownership of durable goods more affordable. The authors show that if rental income is low, in a presence of a peer-to-peer sharing market, the rate of ownership and usage of durable goods is low
- $K_{i,t}$ is the stock of capital
- $fee_t^{platform}$ is the access fee to the digital platform. Although digital platforms charge a fee to both sellers and renters, we assume that this fee is already embedded in the price of sharing energy services paid by the users.
- u_t is the fraction of time the owner uses its durable good stock for home-produced energy services. Households are characterized by the use rate of their durable good stock, or put differently by the time they are willing to use their durable good stock. The use rate is uniformly distributed in the interval $[0,1]$ and the usage is exogenously determined. [3] points out that the proportion of time devoted to the use of a durable good is usually constant for many durable goods. We tend to have the same use pattern of a good regardless of its lifespan. Also, the propensity to match sellers to renters in the sharing market equals one, so they are immediately matched. This assumption is reasonable in the long run
- μ_t is the fraction of time the sharing firm decides to rent durable goods during the time they are available $(1-u)$ such as in [4]. It is uniformly distributed in the interval $[0,1]$.
- $TR_{i,t}$ is the public transfers toward households
- $TB_{i,t}$ is the trade balance that enters the budget constraint as a net foreign debt flow
 $PS_{i,t}$ is the primary surplus of the government. If $PS_{i,t} < 0$, the primary surplus is a lump-sum tax and a lump-sum transfer otherwise.
- $(Carbon_{i,t}^{redis}, EPR_{i,t}^{redis})$ are the carbon tax and EPR fee redistribution mechanisms. These redistribution mechanisms can be activated or not.

In the model, the constant relative risk aversion (CRRA) utility function does not include any disutility from work. We consider that households supply work inelastically at each period.

A.0.2 Constrained household

There is a fraction $(1 - \omega_t^{lowcarbon} - \omega_t^{cautious})$ of households called the constrained household that chooses intratemporally a basket of different types of goods and services, and chooses intertemporally semidurable and durable good stock. The constrained household is constrained by its liquidities, and they cannot save part of its income into capital assets.

The constrained household intertemporally maximizes its utility function by choosing the optimal composition of its consumption basket and its asset portfolio subject to a budget constraint. The maximization program of its utility is as follows:

$$\max \beta \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{(C_{const,t} - h_{const,t} C_{const,t-1})^{1-\sigma^{ies}} - 1}{1 - \sigma^{ies}} \quad (A3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} s.t. \quad & (1 + \tau^{vat}) \left[p_{nd,t} ND_{const,t} + p_{sd,t} Inv_{const,t}^{semidurable} + p_{d,t} (Inv_{const,t}^{newdurable} + Inv_{const,t}^{newdurable}) \right. \\ & \left. + (p_{share,t} ES_{const,t}^{sharing}) + (p_{h,t}^{el} + \tau_{h,t}^{el}) El_{const,t} + (p_{h,t}^{nel} + \tau_{h,t}^{nel}) Nel_{const,t} \right] \\ & + p_{d,t} fee_{durable,t}^{epr} (Inv_{const,t}^{newdurable} + Inv_{const,t}^{newdurable}) + p_{sd,t} fee_{semidurable,t}^{epr} Inv_{const,t}^{semidurable} \\ & + \tau_t^{deposit} (1 - \omega_{mun,t}^{recycle}) \left[\frac{M_{nondurable,t}}{Y_{nondurable,t}} (Z_{nondurable,t}^{domestic} + materialintensity_t^{nondurable} \right. \\ & \left. IMP_{nondurable,t}) \frac{ND_{const,t}}{ND_t} + Materialstock_t^{semidurable} \delta_t^{sd} \frac{SD_{const,t}}{SD_t} \right] \\ & + p_{repair,t} (1 + \tau_t^{vatreduced}) (1 - bonus_t^{durable}) Inv_{const,t}^{repair,durable} \\ & = (1 - \tau^l) w_t L_{const,t} + r_{const,t}^d (1 - fee_t^{platform}) (1 - \tau_t^{sharing}) (1 - u_t) \mu_t D_{const,t} \\ & + TR_t + Carbon_{const,t}^{redis} + EPR_{const,t}^{redis} \end{aligned} \quad (A4)$$

A.0.3 Consumption basket

All 3 types of households share the same technology of consumption. The consumption basket of goods and services of households of lifestyle $l = (lowcarbon, cautious, constrained)$, $C_{l,t}$, is a nested Constant Elasticity Substitution (CES) function of non-durable goods $ND_{l,t}$, semi-durable goods $SD_{l,t}$, and aggregate energy services $ES_{l,t}$ with some degree of substitution σ^c :

$$C_{l,t} = \left[\alpha_t^{nes} \left(\left(\alpha_t^x N D_{l,t} \frac{\sigma^{nes}-1}{\sigma^{nes}} + \alpha_t^{sd} S D_{l,t} \frac{\sigma^{nes}-1}{\sigma^{nes}} \right)^{\frac{\sigma^{nes}}{\sigma^{nes}-1}} \right)^{\frac{\sigma^c-1}{\sigma^c}} + \alpha_t^{es} E S_{l,t} \frac{\sigma^c-1}{\sigma^c} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^c}{\sigma^c-1}} \quad (A5)$$

The aggregate energy services $E S_{l,t}$ is a CES function of home-produced energy services $E S_{l,t}^{home}$ and sharing energy services $E S_{l,t}^{sharing}$ with some degree of substitutability σ^{es} and lifestyle-specific preferences for sharing services $\alpha_t^{sharing}$ and α_t^{home} :

$$E S_{l,t} = \left(\alpha_t^{sharing} E S_{l,t}^{sharing} \frac{\sigma^{es}-1}{\sigma^{es}} + \alpha_t^{home} E S_{l,t}^{home} \frac{\sigma^{es}-1}{\sigma^{es}} \right)^{\frac{\sigma^{es}}{\sigma^{es}-1}} \quad (A6)$$

Home-produced energy services $E S_{l,t}^{home}$ are produced by households from aggregate energy $E_{l,t}^{add}$, and the use rate u_t of durable goods $D_{l,t}$ with some degree of substitutability σ^{home} (refer to [5], [6], and [7]):

$$E S_{l,t}^{home} = \left[\alpha_t^d (u_t D_{l,t}) \frac{\sigma^{home}-1}{\sigma^{home}} + \alpha_t^e (E_{l,t}) \frac{\sigma^{home}-1}{\sigma^{home}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^{home}}{\sigma^{home}-1}} \quad (A7)$$

Home-production of services derives from the household production theory (refer to [8], [9], and [10]) for which households become a producer of services for their own needs.

Aggregate energy $E_{l,t}$ is a CES function of electricity and non-electricity energy :

$$E_{l,t} = \left[\alpha_t^{el} (A_t^{el} E_{l,t}) \frac{\sigma_i^e-1}{\sigma_i^e} + \alpha_t^{nel} (A_t^{nel} N e_{l,t}) \frac{\sigma_i^e-1}{\sigma_i^e} \right]^{\frac{\sigma_i^e}{\sigma_i^e-1}} \quad (A8)$$

The aggregate price of energy $p_{l,t}^e$ ensures that the following equation holds : $p_{l,t}^e E_{l,t} = (p_{h,t}^{el} + \tau_{h,t}^{el}) E_{l,t} + (p_{h,t}^{nel} + \tau_{h,t}^{nel}) N e_{l,t}$.

$$p_{l,t}^e = \left[(\alpha_t^{el})^{1-\sigma_i^e} ((p_{h,t}^{el} + \tau_{h,t}^{el}) A_t^{el})^{1-\sigma_i^e} + (\alpha_t^{nel})^{1-\sigma_i^e} ((p_{h,t}^{nel} + \tau_{h,t}^{nel}) A_t^{nel})^{1-\sigma_i^e} \right]^{\frac{1}{1-\sigma_i^e}} \quad (A9)$$

The energy efficiency of fuels for end-uses is impacted by relative evolution of repaired durable goods compared to new durable goods. Indeed, repairing old durable goods can impact negatively the energy efficiency of end-uses at the aggregate level as the old stock has the energy efficiency of years ago (refer to [11]). In its current version, CIRCEE does not assume different vintages of durable goods with different energy efficiencies. Therefore, we assume a linear relationship between the evolution of repaired durable goods and fuel energy efficiency for simplicity. In the model, repaired durable goods have the energy efficiency (t-1)'s durable good stock and new durable goods have the energy efficiency of today's durable good stock. Fuel energy efficiency for households evolves as follows:

$$A_{l,t}^{nel} = \frac{Inv_{l,t}^{newdurable} + Inv_{l,t}^{newdurable}}{Inv_{l,t}^{newdurable} + Inv_{l,t}^{newdurable} + Inv_{l,t}^{repairdurable}} A_t^{nel} + \frac{Inv_{l,t}^{repairdurable}}{Inv_{l,t}^{newdurable} + Inv_{l,t}^{newdurable} + Inv_{l,t}^{repairdurable}} A_{t-1}^{nel} \quad (A10)$$

A.0.4 Investments in durable assets

A.0.4.1 Households' investment decision and the user cost approach

Low-carbon and cautious households invest in three assets: capital, durable energy-using goods and semi-durable goods. The constrained households invest in 2 different durable assets: durable energy-using goods and semi-durable goods. Semi-durable and durable goods are considered assets as they can be used as collateral against future shocks. Indeed, households can sell part of their stock to cushion a negative shock on their income or expenses. Besides, households have the option to repair a portion of their durable and capital goods stock.

As in [12], the durable good investment decisions for home production of energy services and those that are for the sharing sector are not independent from each other. Households decide how much durable goods stock they want to accumulate at the aggregate level. The investment decision is broken down into 2 parts for repaired and new durable goods, but not for shared durable goods and home production.

A.0.4.2 Laws of motion

Semi-durable goods, durable goods, and capital good accumulate as follows:

$$S D_{l,t+1} = (1 - \delta_t^{sd}) S D_{l,t} + Inv_{l,t}^{semidurable} \quad (A11)$$

$$K_{i,t+1} = (1 - \delta_t^k) K_{i,t} + Inv_{i,t}^{capital} (1 - AC_{i,t}^{capital}) \quad (A12)$$

where,

- $SD_{l,t+1}$ is tomorrow's stock of semi-durable goods
- δ_t^{sd} is the depreciation rate of semi-durable goods

Households can choose whether to repair a part of their depreciated durable good stock or buy new durable goods. We assume that the imperfect substitution between repaired durable assets and newly produced durable asset occurs in the investment phase rather than in the production phase. There are actually three types of investments in this context. The first type, $Inv_{l,t}^{newdurable}$, involves investing in new durable goods to increase the asset stock. The second type, $Inv_{l,t}^{newdurable}$, involves investing in new durable goods to replace a portion of the depreciated asset stock. Lastly, the third type, $Inv_{l,t}^{repairdurable}$, involves investing in repaired durable goods to extend the lifespan of a portion of the depreciated asset stock.

To replace their depreciated durable good stock, household can repair and buy new durable goods according to :

$$Inv_{l,t}^{depdurable} (1 - AC_{l,t}^{depdurable}) = \delta_t^d D_{l,t} \quad (A13)$$

To increase their durable good stock, they can buy new durable goods as follows:

$$D_{l,t+1} = D_{l,t} + Inv_{l,t}^{newdurable} (1 - AC_{l,t}^{newdurable}) \quad (A14)$$

where, $Inv_{l,t}^{depdurable}$ is an investment composite CES function of new investment and repair investment to replace the depreciated durable energy-using goods, respectively $\delta_t^d D_{l,t}$, and is defined as follows:

$$Inv_{l,t}^{depdurable} = \left[\alpha_{l,t}^{newdurable} (Inv_{l,t}^{newdurable})^{\frac{\sigma^{inv,d}-1}{\sigma^{inv,d}}} + \alpha_{l,t}^{repairdurable} (Inv_{l,t}^{repairdurable})^{\frac{\sigma^{inv,d}-1}{\sigma^{inv,d}}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^{inv,d}}{\sigma^{inv,d}-1}} \quad (A15)$$

where,

- $D_{l,t+1}$ is tomorrow's stock of durable goods
- $\delta_{l,t}^d$ the depreciation rate of durable goods
- $(\alpha_{l,t}^{newdurable}, \alpha_{l,t}^{repairdurable})$ are distribution parameters
- $(Inv_{l,t}^{newdurable}, Inv_{l,t}^{repairdurable})$ are investments in newly produced and repaired durable goods to replace the depreciated stock of durable goods
- $Inv_{l,t}^{newdurable}$ are investments in new durable goods
- $(AC_{l,t}^{newdurable}, AC_{l,t}^{depdurable})$ are investment adjustment costs

Low-carbon and cautious households have different saving rates. The Low-carbon households is considered to be more endowed and have a higher saving rate than the Cautious household. This aligns with the lifestyle types defined in [13], where resourceful, active, and cautious households are not liquidity constraints and have rather high incomes compared to the constrained households.

Following [14], the adjustment costs per unit of durable and capital asset of type $asset = [depdurable, newdurable, capital]$ are determined by:

$$AC_t^{asset} = \frac{\vartheta^{asset}}{2} \left(\frac{Inv_t^{asset}}{Inv_{t-1}^{asset} (1 + g^l + g^n + g^l \cdot g^n)} - 1 \right)^2 \quad (A16)$$

where ϑ^{asset} is the adjustment cost parameter.

A.1 Sectors of production

A.1.1 Material firms

A.1.1.1 Primary material producing firm

The firm maximizes its profit defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \max \pi_{prim,t} = & p_{prim,t} Y_{prim,t} - p_t^e E_{prim,t} - w_t L_{prim,t} - r_t K_{prim,t} \\ & - \left[p_t^{raw} + \left(\tau_t^{iw} (1 - \omega_{industrial,t}^{recycle}) + collection_t \right) \gamma_{prim,t} \right] Raw_t \end{aligned} \quad (A17)$$

where,

- $\pi_{prim,t}$ is the profit of the firm
- $p_{prim,t}$ is the exogenous price of primary materials on international markets
- $Y_{prim,t}$ is the production of primary materials
- p_t^e the zero-profit price of energy
- $E_{prim,t}$ is the energy input
- p_t^{raw} is the exogenous price of raw materials
- τ_t^{iw} is the landfill industrial waste tax
- $\omega_{indus,t}^{recycle}$ industrial waste that is recyclable
- $collection_t$ is the industrial waste collection/sorting/transportation (to waste management facility) unit cost charged by municipalities
- $\gamma_{prim,t}$ is the material leakage during the production process
- Raw_t is the raw material inputs
- w_t is nominal wages
- $L_{prim,t}$ is the total number of hours worked
- r_t is the rental rate of capital
- $K_{prim,t}$ is the stock of capital.

The primary material producing firm produces, in a competitive environment, from a CES production function that combines labor, capital, energy, and raw materials input defined as follows:

$$Y_{prim,t} = \left[\alpha_{prim}^{kle} (KLE_{prim,t})^{\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} + \alpha_{prim,t}^{raw} ((1 - \gamma_{prim,t}) Raw_t)^{\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma}{\sigma-1}} \quad (A18)$$

where $KLE_{prim,t}$ is a CES composite of capital-labor and energy inputs and is defined as follows:

$$KLE_{prim,t} = \left[\alpha_{prim}^{kl} (KL_{prim,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{kle}-1}{\sigma^{kle}}} + \alpha_{prim,t}^e (E_{prim,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{kle}-1}{\sigma^{kle}}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^{kle}}{\sigma^{kle}-1}} \quad (A19)$$

where $KL_{prim,t}$ is a CES composite of capital and labor inputs and is defined as follows:

$$KL_{prim,t} = \left[\alpha_{prim}^k (K_{prim,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{kl}-1}{\sigma^{kl}}} + \alpha_{prim}^l (A_t^{labor} L_{prim,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{kl}-1}{\sigma^{kl}}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^{kl}}{\sigma^{kl}-1}} \quad (A20)$$

where A_t^{labor} is labor-saving technical progress.

Aggregate energy $E_{prim,t}$ is a CES function of electricity and non-electricity energy:

$$E_{prim,t} = \left[\alpha_t^{el} (A_t^{el} El_{prim,t})^{\frac{\sigma^e-1}{\sigma^e}} + \alpha_t^{nel} (A_t^{nel} Nel_{prim,t})^{\frac{\sigma^e-1}{\sigma^e}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^e}{\sigma^e-1}} \quad (A21)$$

A.1.1.2 Secondary material producing firm

We assume that the waste management firm is a state-designated firm that collects and recycles into secondary materials the waste from households and industries. A fixed proportion of waste is recycled and supplied to the waste management firm at no cost, meaning that waste supply is price inelastic. The hypothesis of price inelasticity is not too strong because the agents of the economy cannot store waste indefinitely by themselves. The model assumes that there is no waste market that emerges between countries. Furthermore, as in [15], we assume that the sorting, collection, disassembly, and recycling of waste is instantaneous. This hypothesis is not too strong, as the time step of the model is yearly.

The waste management firm maximizes its profit defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \max \pi_{secd,t} = & p_{secd,t} Y_{secd,t} - p_t^e E_{secd,t} - w_t L_{secd,t} - r_t K_{secd,t} \\ & - \left(\tau_t^{iw} (1 - \omega_{indus,t}^{recycle}) + collection_t \right) \gamma_{secd,t} RecyclableWaste_t \end{aligned} \quad (A22)$$

where,

- $\pi_{secd,t}$ is the profit of the firm
- $p_{secd,t}$ is the final price of secondary materials. The price of secondary materials evolves as follows:

$$p_{secd,t} = p_{prim,t} + sub_{secd,t} \quad (A23)$$

We assume that secondary materials that are bought by firms are of close quality to primary materials, else the firm would not buy the material if it were not the case. To cover the total costs of the recycling activities, the government

gives a subsidy that covers the difference between the marginal costs of the recycling activities and the price of primary materials on international markets.

- $Y_{secd,t}$ is the production of primary materials
- τ_t^{iw} is the landfill industrial waste tax
- $\omega_{indus,t}^{recycle}$ the landfilling rate of industrial waste
- $collection_t$ is the industrial waste collection/sorting/transportation (to waste management facility) unit cost charged by municipalities
- $\gamma_{secd,t}$ is the material leakage during the production process
- $RecyclableWaste_t$ is the recyclable waste input
- $subsidies_{secd,t}$ is subsidies to the recycling sector.

The secondary material-producing firm produces, in a competitive environment, from a CES function that combines labor, capital, energy, and waste defined as follows:

$$Y_{secd,t} = \left[\alpha_{secd}^{kle} (KLE_{secd,t})^{\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} + \alpha_{secd,t}^{waste} ((1 - \gamma_{secd,t}) RecyclableWaste_t)^{\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma}{\sigma-1}} \quad (A24)$$

where $\gamma_{secd,t}$ is the material leakage parameter of the firm, i.e. the ability of the recycling facility to minimize the loss of materials during the recycling process as [16] and [17].

$KLE_{secd,t}$ is a CES composite of capital-labor and energy inputs and is defined as follows:

$$KLE_{secd,t} = \left[\alpha_{secd}^{kl} (KL_{secd,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{kle}-1}{\sigma^{kle}}} + \alpha_{secd,t}^e (E_{secd,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{kle}-1}{\sigma^{kle}}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^{kle}}{\sigma^{kle}-1}} \quad (A25)$$

where $KL_{secd,t}$ is a CES composite of capital and labor inputs and is defined as follows:

$$KL_{secd,t} = \left[\alpha_{secd}^k (K_{secd,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{kl}-1}{\sigma^{kl}}} + \alpha_{secd}^l (A_t^{labor} L_{secd,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{kl}-1}{\sigma^{kl}}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^{kl}}{\sigma^{kl}-1}} \quad (A26)$$

Aggregate energy $E_{secd,t}$ is a CES function of electricity and non-electricity energy:

$$E_{secd,t} = \left[\alpha_t^{el} (A_t^{el} El_{secd,t})^{\frac{\sigma^e-1}{\sigma^e}} + \alpha_t^{nel} (A_t^{nel} Nel_{secd,t})^{\frac{\sigma^e-1}{\sigma^e}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^e}{\sigma^e-1}} \quad (A27)$$

A.1.2 Final goods production firms

A.1.2.1 Firms decisions

The final good sectors produce from capital, labor, electricity, fuels, primary materials and secondary materials as production factors (refer to A1). As in [18] and [19], the good-producing firms incur green product design costs that are quadratic and increase with green design parameters. It is the cost of increment in durability and recyclability. The quadratic form reflects decreasing returns in the design attributes.

Each firm $j \in (nondurable, semidurable, durable, capital)$ maximizes its profit defined as follows:

$$\max \pi_{j,t} = (p_{j,t}^{dom} + greendesign_{j,t}) Y_{j,t} - p_{j,t}^e E_{j,t} - w_t L_{j,t} - r_t K_{j,t} - p_{j,t}^m M_{j,t} \quad (A28)$$

where,

- $\pi_{j,t}$ is the profit of the j-good producing firm
- $p_{j,t}^{dom}$ is the price of j-good
- $Y_{j,t}$ is the production of the j-good
- $greendesign_{j,t}$ the premium for green product design
- $p_{j,t}^m$ is the aggregate zero-profit price of materials
- $M_{j,t}$ is the aggregate material input of the j-good firm

The production process of each firm follows a hybrid nested CES production technology. The ((Capital-Labor)-Energy)-Material structure follows the one of [20]:

$$Y_{j,t} = \left[\alpha_j^{kle} (KLE_{j,t})^{\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} + \alpha_j^{material} (M_{j,t})^{\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma}{\sigma-1}} \quad (A29)$$

To ensure a minimal material balance and no excess dematerialization of the economy, σ^j the substitution elasticity is comprised between]0; 1[. In addition, to verify the thermodynamic efficiency condition that limits the transformation capacity of materials into goods, $\gamma_{j,t}$ a material leakage parameter is related to the material inputs (see below), and the

Fig. A1: The nested CES tree of new products sectors. Each intermediate nests has some degree of in-substitutability.

distribution parameters comprise $]0; 1[$. Early work from [21] and [22] advocated for a CES function with an elasticity of substitution strictly inferior to one.

On top the profit maximization problem that the final good firms face, we add an other optimization problem that minimizes an additive CES nest for materials, $M(j, t)^{add}$, under the constraint of material balance. This optimization problems gives the amount of primary and secondary materials used in the production process, while verifying the material balance. Additive material input $M_{j,t}^{add}$ is a volume-preserving CES function à la [23] that minimizes the CES aggregation of material cost components under the constraint of material balance and is equal to $(pcomposite_{j,t}^m M_{j,t})$. This ensures that the 1st law of thermodynamics is verified. The minimization problem is the same as the household energy problem:

$$\min M_{j,t}^{add} = (1 - \gamma_{j,t}) A_{j,t}^m \left[\alpha_{j,t}^{prim} \left[\left(p_t^{prim} + \left(\tau_t^{iw} (1 - \omega_{indus,t}^{recycle}) + collection_t \right) \gamma_{j,t} \right) M_{j,t}^{prim} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^m}{\sigma^m - 1}} + \alpha_{j,t}^{secd} \left[\left(p_t^{secd} + \left(\tau_t^{iw} (1 - \omega_{indus,t}^{recycle}) + collection_t \right) \gamma_{j,t} \right) M_{j,t}^{secd} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^m}{\sigma^m - 1}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^m - 1}{\sigma^m}} \quad (A30)$$

$$s.t. M_{j,t} = M_{j,t}^{prim} + M_{j,t}^{secd} \quad (A31)$$

where,

- τ_t^{iw} is the industrial waste tax
- $\omega_{indus,t}^{recycle}$ industrial waste that is recyclable
- $collection_t$ is the industrial waste collection/sorting/transportation (to waste management facility) unit cost charged by municipalities
- $\gamma_{j,t}$ is the material leakage of the j -good producing firm

In addition to the minimization problem, we need to incorporate 2 different prices of aggregate material, one that comes from the resolution of the minimization problem $pcomposite_{j,t}^m$, called the composite price, and one that makes profits equal to zero $p_{j,t}^m$, called the zero-profit price:

$$pcomposite_{j,t}^m = (1 - \gamma_{j,t}) A_{j,t}^m \left[(\alpha_{j,t}^{prim})^{1-\sigma^m} \left(p_t^{prim} + \left(\tau_t^{iw} (1 - \omega_{indus,t}^{recycle}) + collection_t \right) \gamma_{j,t} \right)^{-\sigma^m} + (\alpha_{j,t}^{secd})^{1-\sigma^m} \left(p_t^{secd} + \left(\tau_t^{iw} (1 - \omega_{indus,t}^{recycle}) + collection_t \right) \gamma_{j,t} \right)^{-\sigma^m} \right]^{-\frac{1}{\sigma^m}} \quad (A32)$$

$$p_{j,t}^m = (pcomposite_{j,t}^m)^{\sigma^m} ((1 - \gamma_{j,t}) A_{j,t}^m)^{1-\sigma^m} \left[(\alpha_{j,t}^{prim})^{1-\sigma^m} \left(p_t^{prim} + \left(\tau_t^{iw} (1 - \omega_{indus,t}^{recycle}) + collection_t \right) \gamma_{j,t} \right)^{1-\sigma^m} + (\alpha_{j,t}^{secd})^{1-\sigma^m} \left(p_t^{secd} + \left(\tau_t^{iw} (1 - \omega_{indus,t}^{recycle}) + collection_t \right) \gamma_{j,t} \right)^{1-\sigma^m} \right] \quad (A33)$$

The average price of materials $p_{j,t}^m$ ensures that the following equation holds: $p_{j,t}^m M_{j,t} = (p_t^{prim} + (\tau_t^{iw}(1 - \omega_{indus,t}^{recycle}) + collection_t)\gamma_{j,t})M_{j,t}^{prim} + (p_t^{secd} + (\tau_t^{iw}(1 - \omega_{indus,t}^{recycle}) + collection_t)\gamma_{j,t})M_{j,t}^{secd}$.

$KLE_{j,t}$ is a CES composite of capital-labor and energy inputs and is defined as follows:

$$KLE_{j,t} = \left[\alpha_j^{kl} (KL_{j,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{kle}-1}{\sigma^{kle}}} + \alpha_{j,t}^e (E_{j,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{kle}-1}{\sigma^{kle}}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^{kle}}{\sigma^{kle}-1}} \quad (A34)$$

where $KL_{j,t}$ is a CES composite of capital and labor inputs and is defined as follows:

$$KL_{j,t} = \left[\alpha_j^k (K_{j,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{kl}-1}{\sigma^{kl}}} + \alpha_j^l (A_t^{labor} L_{j,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{kl}-1}{\sigma^{kl}}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^{kl}}{\sigma^{kl}-1}} \quad (A35)$$

Aggregate energy $E_{j,t}$ is a CES function of electricity and non-electricity energy:

$$E_{j,t} = \left[\alpha_t^{el} (A_t^{el} El_{j,t})^{\frac{\sigma^e-1}{\sigma^e}} + \alpha_t^{nel} (A_t^{nel} Nel_{j,t})^{\frac{\sigma^e-1}{\sigma^e}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^e}{\sigma^e-1}} \quad (A36)$$

Similar to [18] and [19], firms can incur green product design costs $greendesign_{j,t}$ that are quadratic and increase with green design parameters. The green product design unit cost for sector j evolves as follows:

$$greendesign_{j,t} = \frac{\xi_{j,t}^{greendesign}}{Y_{j,t}} \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\delta_{j,t}}{\delta_{j,t-1}} - 1 \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\omega_{indus,t}}{\omega_{indus,t-1}} - 1 \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\omega_{mun,t}}{\omega_{mun,t-1}} - 1 \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{A_{j,t}^m}{A_{j,t-1}^m} - 1 \right)^2 \right] \quad (A37)$$

where,

- $\xi_{j,t}^{greendesign}$ is the green product design cost parameter
- $Y_{j,t}$ is the good production of firm j
- $\delta_{j,t}$ is the “natural” (obsolescence) depreciation rate of good j
- $(\omega_{indus,t}, \omega_{mun,t})$ are the recyclability rate of industrial and municipal waste
- $A_{j,t}^m$ is the material productivity parameter

A.1.2.2 The substitution elasticity in CES functions augmented by energy and material inputs

In CES functions, when the substitution elasticity is constrained between $]0,1[$, inputs are imperfect gross complements (the perfect complementary case would be the Leontief function), meaning that no substitution, whether it be imperfect substitution (CES function with elasticity strictly superior to 1) or perfect substitution (linear function) can be made between the inputs. If we were to have a substitution elasticity strictly superior to 1, then we could end up with a risk of having energy and/or material approaching 0 in the production function. Constraining the substitution elasticity between $]0,1[$ allows us to rule out the possibility of an economy without energy or materials, meaning that all inputs are essential in the production process of the good.

Having a substitution elasticity strictly inferior to 1, gives negative exponent in the CES function, which rules out the possibility of having an input set to 0 in the production process. Here is an example of a CES function with only capital and labor inputs. The CES reads as follows:

$$Y_{j,t} = \left[\alpha_t^k (K_{j,t})^{\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} + \alpha_t^l (L_{j,t})^{\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma}{\sigma-1}} \quad (A38)$$

If $\sigma = 0.5$,

$$Y_{j,t} = \frac{1}{\alpha_t^k \left(\frac{1}{K_{j,t}} \right) + \alpha_t^l \left(\frac{1}{L_{j,t}} \right)} \quad (A39)$$

If we take the limit of the production function for one input approaching 0 (the other input is fixed), the denominator of the previous equation would be equal to ∞ and the production equal to 0 irrespective of the level of the other input:

$$\lim_{L \rightarrow 0} Y = 0 \quad (A40)$$

Therefore, K or L cannot be equal to 0, they are both essential in the production process because, any of them tending toward zero implies that the production of the good is also tending toward zero.

A.1.3 Circular service-producing firms

A.1.3.1 The repairing services firm

The maximization program of the repair firm is as follows:

$$\max \pi_{repair,t} = p_{repair,t} Y_{repair,t} - w_t L_{repair,t} - r_t K_{repair,t} \quad (A41)$$

where, $Y_{repair,t}$ is a CES function of labor and capital as follows:

$$Y_{repair,t} = \left[\alpha_{repair,t}^k (K_{repair,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{kl}-1}{\sigma^{kl}}} + \alpha_{repair,t}^l (A_t^{labor} L_{repair,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{kl}-1}{\sigma^{kl}}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^{kl}}{\sigma^{kl}-1}} \quad (A42)$$

where, $(\alpha_{repair,t}^k, \alpha_{repair,t}^l)$, the distribution parameters, are made time-dependent to analyze scenarios where the repair sector undergoes automation.

A.1.3.2 The sharing (energy) services firm

The sharing firm maximizes its profits defined as follows:

$$\max \pi_{share,t} = p_{share,t} Y_{share,t} - p_t^e E_{share,t} - w_t L_{share,t} - (1 - fee_t^{platform}) \sum_l r_{l,t}^d (1 - u_t) \mu_t D_{l,t} \quad (A43)$$

where,

- $fee_t^{platform}$ is the fee to access the digital platform of the sharing firm. The fee is a commission that is extracted by the sharing firm to owners of durable goods for successfully matching owners to renters. We assume that the probability of success is equal to 1 and no matching frictions exist given the long term horizon of the model. Owners and renters match immediately on the sharing platform.
- $\sum_l (1 - u_t) \mu_t D_{l,t}$ is the total availability of durable goods among the 3 households. The sharing firm produces sharing energy services by choosing the time μ_t it wants to use the available durable goods $\sum_l (1 - u_t) D_{l,t}$.

The production of sharing energy services $Y_{share,t}$ is a CES function as follows:

$$Y_{share,t} = \left[\alpha_{share,t}^l (A_t^{labor} L_{share,t})^{\frac{\sigma_{share}-1}{\sigma_{share}}} + \alpha_{share,t}^{es} (ES_{share,t})^{\frac{\sigma_{share}-1}{\sigma_{share}}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma_{share}}{\sigma_{share}-1}} \quad (A44)$$

where, $ES_{share,t}$ is the durable-energy CES nest defined as follows:

$$ES_{share,t} = \left[\alpha_{share,t}^d \left(\sum_l (1 - u_t) \mu_t D_{l,t} \right)^{\frac{\sigma^{es}-1}{\sigma^{es}}} + \alpha_{share,t}^e (E_{share,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{es}-1}{\sigma^{es}}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^{es}}{\sigma^{es}-1}} \quad (A45)$$

where, $E_{share,t}$ is the additive CES function of energy and follows the same specification as the other sectors (refer to section 4.2.1.1.). Additionally, due to data availability, we are assuming that the parameters governing the CES nest for energy services produced by the sharing firm are the same as the CES nest for energy services produced by households.

Finally, for comparability between households' home-produced energy services and sharing energy services, we impose that the value of $Y_{share,t}$ to be equal to the value of $ES_{share,t}$.

A.2 Trade

A.2.1 Commodities trade

The total imports of resources are defined as follows:

$$IMP_t^{resource} = p_t^{raw} Raw_t + p_t^{nel} \left(\sum_j Nel_{j,t} + Nel_{share,t} + Nel_{prim,t} + Nel_{secd,t} \right) + p_{h,t}^{nel} \sum_l Nel_{l,t} \quad (A46)$$

where prices are expressed in domestic currency.

The final demand for refined materials $m = prim, secd$ of the domestic economy $Demand_{m,t}^{domestic}$ is produced by a perfectly competitive firm combining domestically produced refined materials $Z_{m,t}^{domestic}$ and imports $IMP_{m,t}$ using the following CES Argmington aggregator as in [24]. The profit maximization of the sector is defined as follows:

$$\max p_{m,t} Demand_{m,t}^{domestic} - p_{m,t} Z_{m,t}^{domestic} - p_{m,t} IMP_{m,t} \quad (A47)$$

where, $p_{m,t}$ is the price of materials on international markets expressed in domestic currency. Domestic demand for materials $Demand_{m,t}^{domestic}$ is a CES specification defined as follows:

$$Demand_{m,t}^{domestic} = \left[\alpha_{m,t}^{domestic} (Z_{m,t}^{domestic})^{\frac{\sigma^{imports}-1}{\sigma^{imports}}} + \alpha_{m,t}^{imp} (IMP_{m,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{imports}-1}{\sigma^{imports}}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^{imports}}{\sigma^{imports}-1}} \quad (A48)$$

where $Demand_{m,t}^{domestic} = \sum_j M_{m,j,t}$.

The final demand for refined materials of the foreign economy follows the same profit maximization problem and CES specification:

$$Demand_{m,t}^{foreign} = \left[\alpha_{m,t}^{foreign} (Z_{m,t}^{foreign})^{\frac{\sigma^{exports}-1}{\sigma^{exports}}} + \alpha_{m,t}^{exp} (EXP_{m,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{exports}-1}{\sigma^{exports}}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^{exports}}{\sigma^{exports}-1}} \quad (A49)$$

where the foreign demand for materials is equal to a constant share of materials produced by the domestic economy $Demand_{m,t}^{foreign} = share_m^{foreign} Y_{m,t}$.

A.2.2 Final goods trade

A.2.2.1 Import sector

The final demand for goods $g \in (nondurable, semidurable, durable, capital)$ of the domestic economy $Demand_{g,t}^{domestic}$ is produced by perfectly competitive firms combining domestically produced goods $Z_{g,t}^{domestic}$ and imports $IMP_{g,t}$ using the following Armington CES aggregator, as in [24]. The profit maximization of the sector is defined as follows:

$$\max p_{g,t} Demand_{g,t}^{domestic} - p_{g,t}^{dom} Z_{g,t}^{domestic} - p_{g,t}^{fg} (1 + t_{g,t}^{import}) IMP_{g,t} \quad (A50)$$

where,

- $p_{g,t}$ is the aggregate price of good g in domestic currency
- $p_{g,t}^{dom}$ is the domestic price of good g in domestic currency
- $(p_{g,t}^{fg}, t_{g,t}^{import})$ is an index of world consumer prices in domestic currency and the tax on imports

Domestic demand for goods $Demand_{g,t}^{domestic}$ is a CES specification defined as follows:

$$Demand_{g,t}^{domestic} = \left[\alpha_{g,t}^{domestic} (Z_{g,t}^{domestic})^{\frac{\sigma^{imports}-1}{\sigma^{imports}}} + \alpha_{g,t}^{imp} (IMP_{g,t})^{\frac{\sigma^{imports}-1}{\sigma^{imports}}} \right]^{\frac{\sigma^{imports}}{\sigma^{imports}-1}} \quad (A51)$$

where,

- $(\alpha_{g,t}^{domestic}, \alpha_{g,t}^{imp})$ are distribution parameters
- $\sigma^{imports}$ is the substitution elasticity of imports.
- $Demand_{g,t}^{domestic}$ is the sum of households' consumption and government consumption of good g .

A.2.2.2 Export sector

The final demand for goods $g \in (nondurable, semidurable, durable, capital)$ of the foreign economy $Demand_{g,t}^{foreign}$ is produced by perfectly competitive firms combining foreign-produced goods $Z_{g,t}^{foreign}$ and imports $EXP_{g,t}$ using the following CES technology, as in [24]. The total exports of the domestic economy to the foreign economy are as follows:

$$EXP_{g,t} = \left[\alpha_{g,t}^{foreign} \left(\frac{p_{g,t}^{row}}{p_{g,t}^{dom}} \right) \right]^{\sigma^{exports}} Demand_{g,t}^{foreign} \quad (A52)$$

where,

- $\alpha_{g,t}^{row}$ is the distribution parameter
- $p_{g,t}^{row}$ is the aggregate/deflator price of good g in the foreign economy in domestic currency
- $p_{g,t}^{dom}$ is the price of domestically produced good g in the domestic economy in domestic currency
- $\sigma^{exports}$ is the substitution elasticity of exports
- $Demand_{g,t}^{foreign}$ is the demand for goods of the foreign economy. The foreign demand for materials is equal to the (exogenous) share of materials produced by the domestic economy $Demand_{g,t}^{foreign} = share_g^{foreign} Y_{g,t}$.

A.2.3 Trade balance

The trade balance of the economy is defined as follows:

$$TB_t = \sum_g p_{g,t}^{dom} EXP_{g,t} + p_{prim,t} EXP_{prim,t} + p_{secd,t} EXP_{secd,t} - \left(\sum_g p_{g,t}^{fg} IMP_{g,t} + p_{prim,t} IMP_{prim,t} + p_{secd,t} IMP_{secd,t} + IMP_t^{resource} \right) \quad (A53)$$

A.3 The government

Public consumption of non-durable, semi-durable, and durable goods is an exogenous share of market output as in [25]:

$$ND_{gov,t} = share_t^{nondurable} Y_t^{nondurable} \quad (A54)$$

$$Inv_{gov,t}^{semidurable} = share_t^{semidurable} Y_t^{semidurable} \quad (A55)$$

$$Inv_{gov,t}^{durable} = share_t^{durable} Y_t^{durable} \quad (A56)$$

where,

- $(ND_{gov,t}, Inv_{gov,t}^{semidurable}, Inv_{gov,t}^{durable})$ are non-durable, semi-durable and durable good demand from the government
 - $(share_t^{nondurable}, share_t^{semidurable}, share_t^{durable})$ are the (exogenous) good demand to GDP ratios
- Durable and semi-durable public goods accumulate as follows:

$$D_{gov,t+1} = (1 - \delta_t^d) D_{gov,t} + Inv_{gov,t}^{durable} \quad (A57)$$

$$SD_{gov,t+1} = (1 - \delta_t^{sd}) SD_{gov,t} + Inv_{gov,t}^{semidurable} \quad (A58)$$

where,

- $(D_{gov,t+1}, SD_{gov,t+1})$ are tomorrow's stock of durable and semi-durable goods
- $(\delta_t^d, \delta_t^{sd})$ are durable and semi-durable good depreciation rates. In contrast to households, we consider that the government does not repair/refurbish part of its durable asset stock. The depreciation rate here is related to the natural obsolescence rate of goods.

Although households are subject to investment adjustment costs, the government is not subject to them as public spending does not adjust slowly overtime to changes in wealth or other factors such as innovation.

Lump-sum transfers to households TR_t are assumed constant.

According to [26], a balanced budget requires at least one passive policy. In the model, the passive policy corresponds to the redistribution mechanism PS_t . It represents a lump-sum transfer to households if positive and a flat tax to households if negative. Fiscal policies, public spending G_t and social transfers TR_t are active policies in the model. At all times, the government balances. The potential primary fiscal deficit is covered by the low-carbon and cautious households who have access to capital markets. The primary deficit is a good first approximation of the constraints a government face when accumulating debt ([27] and [28]).

Debt is intentionally omitted in the model, similar to the approach taken by [29], [30], and [31]. The primary surplus is a reasonable approximation of the constraints faced by a government when borrowing money. The government fiscal

rules are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
Revenues_t = & \tau^{vat} \left[p_{nd,t} \sum_l ND_{l,t} + p_{sd,t} \sum_l \left(Inv_{l,t}^{semidurable} \right) \right. \\
& + p_{d,t} \left(\sum_l Inv_{l,t}^{newdurable} + \sum_l Inv_{l,t}^{newdurable} \right) + p_{share,t} \sum_l ES_{l,t}^{sharing} \\
& + (p_{h,t}^{el} + \tau_{h,t}^{el}) \sum_l El_{l,t} + (p_{h,t}^{nel} + \tau_{h,t}^{nel}) \sum_l Nel_{l,t} \left. \right] + \tau_{h,t}^{el} \left(\sum_l El_{l,t} + El_{sharing,t} \right) \\
& + \tau_t^{el} \left(\sum_j El_{j,t} + El_{prim,t} + El_{secd,t} \right) + \tau_{h,t}^{nel} \left(\sum_l Nel_{l,t} + Nel_{sharing,t} \right) \\
& \tau_t^{nel} \left(\sum_j Nel_{j,t} + Nel_{prim,t} + Nel_{secd,t} \right) + \tau_t^{deposit} (1 - \omega_{mun,t}^{recycle}) \\
& \left(\frac{M_{nondurable,t}}{Y_{nondurable,t}} \right) \left[(Z_{nondurable,t} + materialintensity_t^{nondurable} IMP_{nondurable,t}) \right. \\
& \left. \frac{\sum_l ND_{l,t}}{\sum_l ND_{l,t} + ND_{gov,t}} + Materialstock_t^{semidurable} \delta_t^{sd} \frac{\sum_l SD_{l,t}}{\sum_l SD_{l,t} + SD_{gov,t}} \right] \\
& + \tau_t^{vatreduced} p_{repair,t} \left(bonus_t^{durable} \sum_l Inv_{l,t}^{repairdurable} \right. \\
& \left. \right) + \tau^l w_t \sum_l L_{l,t} + \tau_t^{sharing} \left(1 - fee_t^{platform} \right) \\
& \sum_l r_{l,t}^d (1 - u_t) \mu_t D_{l,t} + \tau^k r_t \sum_i (1 - \delta_t^k) K_{i,t} + \left(\tau_t^{iw} (1 - \omega_{indus,t}^{recycle}) + collection_t \right) \\
& \left(\sum_j \gamma_{j,t} M_{j,t} + \gamma_{secd,t} RecyclableWaste_t + \gamma_{prim,t} Raw_t \right) \\
& + p_{d,t} fee_{durable,t}^{ep} (Inv_{l,t}^{newdurable} + Inv_{l,t}^{newdurable}) + p_{sd,t} fee_{semidurable,t}^{ep} \\
& Inv_{l,t}^{semidurable} + \sum_g p_{g,t}^{fg} imports_g IMP_{g,t}
\end{aligned} \tag{A59}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Expenses_t = & p_{nd,t} ND_{gov,t} + p_{sd,t} Inv_{gov,t}^{semidurable} + p_{d,t} Inv_{gov,t}^{durable} \\
& + p_{repair,t} \left(bonus_t^{durable} \sum_l Inv_{l,t}^{repairdurable} \right) \\
& + TR_t + \sum_l PS_{i,t} + sub_{secd,t} Y_{secd,t}
\end{aligned} \tag{A60}$$

The industrial waste tax and EPR fees cover part of the subsidies for the recycling sector $subsidies_t^{secd} Y_{secd,t}$. The unit cost of collection and transportation of industrial waste and the tax on household waste cover the collection and transportation costs of municipalities. Subsidies are set endogenously to cover the costs of the recycling sector and ensure a zero-profit rule for the recycling sector.

A.4 Model closure

A.5 Aggregation rules across households

Given that households are identical in each lifestyle group, at the aggregate level, each variable of decision of households V_t follows the following aggregation rules:

$$\begin{aligned}
V_t = & \int_0^1 V_{l,t} dl = \omega_{lowcarbon,t} V_{lowcarbon,t} + \omega_{cautious,t} V_{cautious,t} \\
& + (1 - \omega_{lowcarbon,t} - \omega_{cautious,t}) V_{constrained,t}
\end{aligned} \tag{A61}$$

Each variable in $Q \in (K, Inv^{capital}, AC^{capital})$ follows the following aggregation rules:

$$Q_t = \omega_{lowcarbon,t} Q_{lowcarbon,t} + \omega_{cautious,t} Q_{cautious,t} \quad (A62)$$

where, $(\omega_{lowcarbon,t}, \omega_{cautious,t})$ are the share of each lifestyle in the total population. These exogenous variables are inputs from the LIFE model.

A.5.1 Market clearing condition

The model verifies the following market clearing conditions that equal supply to demand at each time:

- **Labor market**

$$L_t (= 1) = L_{prim,t} + L_{secd,t} + \sum_j L_{j,t} + L_{repair,t} + L_{share,t} \quad (A63)$$

- **Capital market**

$$K_t = (1 + g + n + gn)(K_{prim,t} + K_{secd,t} + \sum_j K_{j,t} + K_{repair,t}) \quad (A64)$$

where, $(1 + g + n + gn)$ is the total growth rate of the economy. The total stock of capital is predetermined, while the split between the sectors is not.

In the case of a multi-sector economy, only the total stock of capital is predetermined. The total stock of the economy can be allocated freely among the various sectors in t . As a result, the capital stock in each sector is determined in t and is not predetermined.

- **Material markets**

$$Y_{prim,t} = Z_{prim,t}^{domestic} + EXP_{prim,t} \quad (A65)$$

$$Y_{secd,t} = Z_{secd,t}^{domestic} + EXP_{secd,t} \quad (A66)$$

- **Non-durable goods market**

$$Y_{nondurable,t} = Z_{nondurable,t}^{domestic} + EXP_{nondurable,t} \quad (A67)$$

- **Semi-durable goods market**

$$Y_{semidurable,t} = Z_{semidurable,t}^{domestic} + EXP_{semidurable,t} \quad (A68)$$

- **Durable goods market**

$$Y_{durable,t} = Z_{durable,t}^{domestic} + EXP_{durable,t} \quad (A69)$$

- **Capital goods market**

$$Y_{capital,t} = Z_{capital,t}^{domestic} + EXP_{capital,t} \quad (A70)$$

- **Sharing energy services market**

$$Y_{share,t} = \sum_l ES_{l,t}^{share} \quad (A71)$$

- **Repair service market**

$$Y_{repair,t} = \sum_l Inv_{l,t}^{repairdurable} \quad (A72)$$

A.6 Material in-use stock and flows, and waste flows

The in-use stocks are defined as follows:

- **Gross additions to the stock**

$$\begin{aligned} AddStock_t &= (1 - \gamma_{semidurable,t}) \left(\frac{M_{semidurable,t}}{Y_{semidurable,t}} \right) [Z_{semidurable,t}^{domestic} + materialintensity_t^{semidurable} IMP_{semidurable,t}] \\ &+ (1 - \gamma_{durable,t}) \left(\frac{M_{durable,t}}{Y_{durable,t}} \right) [Z_{durable,t}^{domestic} + materialintensity_t^{durable} IMP_{durable,t}] \\ &+ (1 - \gamma_{capital,t}) \left(\frac{M_{capital,t}}{Y_{capital,t}} \right) [Z_{capital,t}^{domestic} + materialintensity_t^{capital} IMP_{capital,t}] \end{aligned} \quad (A73)$$

- **Material balance**

$$MatBalance_t = AddStock_t + (1 - \gamma_{nondurable,t}) \left(\frac{M_{nondurable,t}}{Y_{nondurable,t}} \right) [Z_{nondurable,t}^{domestic} + materialintensity_t^{nondurable} IMP_{nondurable,t}]$$

$$\gamma_{nondurable,t} M_{nondurable,t} + \gamma_{semidurable,t} M_{semidurable,t} + \gamma_{durable,t} M_{durable,t} + \gamma_{capital,t} M_{capital,t}$$

$$EXP_{prim,t} + EXP_{secd,t} - (IMP_{prim,t} + IMP_{secd,t} + (1 - \gamma_{prim,t}) Raw_t + (1 - \gamma_{secd,t}) RecyclableWaste_t)$$
(A74)

- **Semi-durable good in-use stock**

$$Materialstock_{t+1}^{semidurable} = Materialstock_t^{semidurable} (1 - \delta_t^{sd}) + (1 - \gamma_{semidurable,t})$$

$$\left(\frac{M_{semidurable,t}}{Y_{semidurable,t}} \right) [Z_{semidurable,t}^{domestic} + materialintensity_t^{semidurable} IMP_{semidurable,t}]$$
(A75)

- **Durable good in-use stock**

$$Materialstock_{t+1}^{durable} = Materialstock_t^{durable} (1 - \delta_t^d) + (1 - \gamma_{durable,t}) \left(\frac{M_{durable,t}}{Y_{durable,t}} \right)$$

$$[Z_{durable,t}^{domestic} + materialintensity_t^{durable} IMP_{durable,t}]$$
(A76)

- **Capital in-use stock**

$$Materialstock_{t+1}^{capital} = Materialstock_t^{capital} (1 - \delta_t^k) + (1 - \gamma_{capital,t}) \left(\frac{M_{capital,t}}{Y_{capital,t}} \right)$$

$$[Z_{capital,t}^{domestic} + materialintensity_t^{capital} IMP_{capital,t}]$$
(A77)

The landfilled/incinerated waste flows are defined as follows:

- **Landfilled/Incinerated industrial waste flows**

$$Waste_t^{indus} = (1 - \omega_{indus,t}^{recycle}) \left(\sum_j \gamma_{j,t} M_{j,t} + \gamma_{prim,t} Raw_t + \gamma_{secd,t} RecyclableWaste_t + Materialstock_t^{capital} \delta_t^k \right)$$
(A78)

- **Landfilled/Incinerated municipal waste flows**

$$Waste_t^{mun} = (1 - \omega_{mun,t}^{recycle}) (Materialstock_t^{durable} \delta_t^d + Materialstock_t^{semidurable} \delta_t^{sd})$$

$$+ (1 - \gamma_{nondurable,t}) \left(\frac{M_{nondurable,t}}{Y_{nondurable,t}} \right) [Z_{nondurable,t}^{domestic} + materialintensity_t^{nondurable} IMP_{nondurable,t}]$$
(A79)

Recyclable waste flows are defined as follows:

- **Recyclable industrial waste flows**

$$Waste_{recyclable,t}^{indus} = \omega_{indus,t}^{recycle} \left(\sum_j \gamma_{j,t} M_{j,t} + \gamma_{prim,t} Raw_t + \gamma_{secd,t} RecyclableWaste_t + Materialstock_t^{capital} \delta_t^k \right)$$
(A80)

- **Recyclable municipal waste flows**

$$Waste_{recyclable,t}^{mun} = \omega_{mun,t}^{recycle} (Materialstock_t^{durable} \delta_t^d + Materialstock_t^{semidurable} \delta_t^{sd} +$$

$$(1 - \gamma_{nondurable,t}) \left(\frac{M_{nondurable,t}}{Y_{nondurable,t}} \right) [Z_{nondurable,t}^{domestic} + materialintensity_t^{nondurable} IMP_{nondurable,t}])$$
(A81)

In the model, waste imports allows the recycling firm to import waste if its needs, $RecyclableWaste_t$, are higher than the total recycled municipal and industrial waste produced in the economy. $Trade_t^{waste}$ is positive if the country imports recyclable waste and negative if it exports recyclable waste to countries where environmental regulation is less stringent :

$$Trade_t^{waste} = RecyclableWaste_t - (Waste_{recyclable,t}^{mun} + Waste_{recyclable,t}^{indus})$$
(A82)

A.7 Units of endogenous variables

The units of the main endogenous variables are given in [A1](#).

Variables	Description	Unit
C_l	Aggregate consumption	JPY
ND_l	Non-durable good consumption	JPY
SD_l	Semi-durable good consumption	JPY
D_l	Durable good consumption	JPY
E_l	Energy consumption of households	MJ
El_l	Electricity consumption	MJ
Nel_l	Non-electricity energy consumption	MJ
$ES_l^{sharing}$	Sharing services	JPY
$Inv_l^{newdurable}$	Households' acquisitions of new durable goods	JPY
$Inv_l^{repairdurable}$	Households' acquisitions of repaired durable goods	JPY
K_i	Capital goods stock	JPY
$Inv_i^{capital}$	Households' acquisitions of capital goods	JPY
L_l	Number of employees	Person
w	Wage rate	JPY
PS	Primary surplus	JPY
TB	Trade balance	JPY
$AC_i^{capital}$	Capital investments adjustment costs	JPY
$AC_l^{newdurable}$	Durable goods investments adjustment costs	JPY
$Y_{prim}, Y_{sec}, Y_j, Y_{sharing}, Y_{repair}$	Output	JPY
Raw	Raw material needs	gram
$E_{prim}, E_{sec}, E_j, E_{sharing}$	Energy use by sectors	MJ
$El_{prim}, El_{sec}, El_j, El_{sharing}$	Electricity use by sectors	MJ
$Nel_{prim}, Nel_{sec}, Nel_j, Nel_{sharing}$	Non-electricity energy use by sectors	MJ
$L_{prim}, L_{sec}, L_j, L_{sharing}, L_{repair}$	Number of employees in sectors	Person
$K_{prim}, K_{sec}, K_j, K_{sharing}, K_{repair}$	Capital inputs of sectors	JPY
$RecyclableWaste$	Waste input of the recycling firm	gram
M_j	Aggregate material input of sectors	gram
M_j^{prim}	Primary material input of sectors	gram
M_j^{sec}	Secondary material input of sectors	gram
r	Rental rate of capital	-
μ	Share of durable goods rented by the sharing firm	-
$IMP^{resource}$	Imports of resources	JPY
$Demand_m^{domestic}$	Domestic demand of goods	gram
$Demand_g^{domestic}$	Domestic demand of materials	JPY
$Z_m^{domestic}$	Domestic production of materials for domestic use	gram
IMP_m	Imports of materials for domestic use	gram
$Z_g^{domestic}$	Domestic production of goods for domestic use	JPY
IMP_g	Imports of goods for domestic use	JPY
EXP_g	Exports of goods	JPY
EXP_m	Exports of materials	gram
ND_{gov}	Government's non-durable goods consumption	JPY
SD_{gov}	Government's semi-durable goods stock	JPY
D_{gov}	Government's durable goods stock	JPY
$Inv_{gov}^{semidurable}$	Government's semi-durable goods acquisitions	JPY
$Inv_{gov}^{durable}$	Government's durable goods acquisitions	JPY
$Revenues$	Government's fiscal revenues	JPY
$Expenses$	Government's fiscal expenses	JPY
$Revenues$	Government's fiscal revenues	JPY
$AddStock$	Additions to the stock	gram
$Materialstock^{semidurable}$	In-use stock of semi-durable goods	gram
$Materialstock^{durable}$	In-use stock of durable goods	gram
$Materialstock^{capital}$	In-use stock of capital goods	gram
$Waste^{indus}$	Landfilled/Incinerated industrial waste	gram
$Waste^{mun}$	Landfilled/Incinerated municipal waste	gram
$Waste_{recyclable}^{indus}$	Recyclable industrial waste	gram
$Waste_{recyclable}^{mun}$	Recyclable municipal waste	gram
$Trade^{waste}$	Trade in waste	gram

Table A1: Variables units of measurement

A.8 Implementation of the model

The model uses Dynare as the software and Matlab as the computational environment. The data formats are in csv and the computation time is between 10 seconds and 2 minutes depending on the scenario implemented.”

A.9 Circular Economy (CE) strategies in CIRCEE

A.9.1 CE strategy implementation in households' equations

Economic and behavioral policy instruments directly impact households' intertemporal and intratemporal consumption and investment decisions. The behavioral and economic instruments used to foster sustainable consumption practices are given in [A2](#).

Table A2: Circular Economy Strategies in CIRCEE

Potting et al. (2017)	Goal in CIRCEE_LIFE	Instruments in CIRCEE_LIFE
R0 : Refuse	Reduce consumption of energy-using durable goods and semi-durable goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lifestyle changes • EPR fees • Import tariffs
R1 : Rethink	Sharing of energy-using durable goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lifestyle changes • Favorable taxation to sharing income • EPR fees
R4 : Repair	Extending the life span instead of buying new energy-using durable goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lifestyle changes • Reduced consumption tax • Repair bonus • EPR fees
R5 : Refurbish	Extending the life span instead of buying new energy-using durable goods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lifestyle changes • EPR fees • Reduced consumption tax

A.9.1.1 Implementation of a higher EPR fee

The increase of EPR fees can impact all R strategies stated in Table above. It can help households transition toward a smarter use of products, shift consumption practices toward circular practices and reduce the consumption of specific products such as electronic and electrical equipment.

Eqs. (A6)-(A8) are the behavioral equations of consumers related to the consumption of energy services produced at home compared to energy services bought on the sharing market, the joint use of durable goods and energy to produce energy services at home, and the energy mix in the production of energy services produced at home. An increase in the EPR fee for durable goods can impact these equations and foster a higher participation rate of households in the economy as it becomes more costly for them to directly own a durable good. In addition, a lower demand for durable goods for personal consumption will decrease the amount of energy consumed jointly with the use of durable goods. This change affects eqs. (A6)-(A8).

Implementation of this policy also affects the aggregate demand for durable goods and sharing services addressed to durable good production and sharing firms (refer to eqs. (A69), (A28)-(A36) for the durable good firm, and (A43)-(A45) for the sharing firm). In CIRCEE, green product design (refer to eq. (A40)) does not endogenously respond to demand. For future research, CIRCEE will include the pricing strategy of final goods producing firms in response to the presence of specific circular sectors such as the repair and sharing sectors. First, an increase in EPR fees can positively impact the supply of sharing services and negatively impact the supply of durable goods in the long run. Therefore, it can negatively affect the input mix used by both firms, in particular the energy and materials needed for the production of these goods. The effect on resource use affects the trade balance (refer to eq. (A53)) and CO2 emissions. This impact can be positive and, as a result of lower trade deficits and lower CO2 emissions, can support green growth. These results will depend largely on how households re-balance their consumption basket, which will have a negative impact on government revenues and expenditure. Second, a higher demand addressed to the sharing firm will increase the time that the sharing firm wants to use the durable good stock of households, increasing the revenues gained from renting out durable goods. This increase in income can lead to an increase in household consumption and investment decisions, which, in turn, affects firms that address demand. The manner in which households re-balance their consumption and investment portfolios can have an initial negative impact on material and energy needs as a result of increasing EPR fees. If households substitute toward the consumption of more material-intensive goods, the initial negative effect can be partially offset.

Furthermore, a higher EPR fee on durable goods can impact the trade-off between repairing durable goods and acquiring new durable goods because of the higher user cost of durable goods (refer to eqs. (A13) and (A16)). The households might want to substitute for repairing durable goods rather than acquiring new ones, which would allow them to continue consuming the same amount of energy services rather than decreasing the production of energy services at

home in response to the higher user cost of durable goods. This decision would increase the share of repaired durable goods in the total stock of durable goods, thus fostering repair services. However, a higher share of repaired durable goods in the total stock of durable goods of the economy can decrease at the aggregate level the level of fuel energy efficiency (refer to eq. (A10)), increasing the need for energy.

Re-balancing the consumption basket has an impact on behavioral equation (A5). Depending on the response to the demand for aggregate energy services, households can choose to move away from the consumption of energy services and consume more non-energy services. Non-energy services comprise non-durable and semi-durable goods. Given the high share of non-durable goods in the total consumption basket, increasing the demand for non-durable goods can increase revenues from taxation of consumption of non-durable goods (refer to eq. (A59)). However, an increase in the EPR fee in durable goods and semi-durable goods resulting in a substitution toward non-durable goods can increase the total material and energy needs of the economy depending on the amount of materials embedded in non-durable compared to semi-durable and durable goods. In view of the potential impact of an increase in the EPR fee on specific final good demand and supply, it will have an impact on the Gross Domestic Product.

As regards in-use stocks and waste flows, an increase in the EPR fee for specific products will have a negative impact on total waste flows (refer to eqs. (A78)-(A81)), and in-use stocks in the economy (refer to eqs. (A73)-(A77)). If an increase in the EPR fee for durable goods decreases the acquisition of durable goods and increases the consumption of non-durable goods, municipal waste flows will increase in the long term and durable good in-use stocks will decrease. This effect depends on whether the household engages in the sharing economy or in repairing services. Engaging in repair services will maintain a part of the durable good in-use stock, while decreasing municipal waste flows as substitution toward non-durable goods will be limited. Participation in sharing services would increase the use of existing stocks of durable goods, which in the long term could lead to a reduction in durable good in-use stocks. However, this effect will depend on whether households will, in the long run, replace part of the durable good stock in response to more intensive use.

As a result of an increase in EPR fees, repairs would inevitably slow down the resource cycle. Engaging in sharing services can slow the resource loop; however, in the long run, it will depend on households' durable good replacement decisions. Finally, the effect of decreasing the consumption of energy services and substituting toward the consumption of non-durable goods on slowing the resource loop is also ambiguous. It may be beneficial or harmful.

A.9.1.2 Labor income tax on sharing income and lifestyle changes

A.9.1.2.1 Labor income tax on sharing income. The decrease in the labor income tax on households' sharing revenues is embedded in the R1 strategies in CIRCEE. It can help households transition toward a smarter use of products and shift consumption practices.

Lowering the income tax on the income received from the sharing platform can incentivize households to share more durable goods on the sharing market. This has a direct impact on household budgetary constraints (refer to eqs. (A2) and (A4)), user costs of durable goods and the demand for sharing services and durable goods (refer to eqs. (A6)-(A7)). A lower income tax will decrease the user cost of durable goods, potentially increasing the demand for durable goods addressed to the durable good firm. As user cost decreases, energy services at home are cheaper. While it is more attractive to rent durable goods to the sharing firm, households might increase their production of energy services at home. Since the substitution elasticity between home-produced and shared energy services is superior to 1 in the model, households might decrease their consumption of shared energy services in response to a higher production of energy services produced at home.

A lower income tax means higher revenues from the sharing market, which could foster higher consumption for all three households, a higher supply of consumption and investment goods (refer to eqs. (A67)-(A70)) in response to higher demand, and a potentially higher GDP. Also, the economy could increase its imports of goods if domestic supply is not enough to cover the higher demand, although we expect this effect to be low (refer to eqs. (A50)-(A51)). As a response to higher demand, the final good firm can increase its demand for material and energy inputs to produce goods (refer to eqs. (A69) and (A28)-(A36)). If the economy decides to increase its imports of goods in response to a higher demand, this can also impact the material intensity of the economy depending on the differentials in material productivity between the country of study in CIRCEE and the rest of the world.

The effect on government revenues could be positive if higher consumption tax revenue offsets the decrease in labor taxation revenue (refer to eq. (A59)). A lower taxation of shared income (shared income is taxed at the labor income tax rate) reduces government revenues, but a lower income tax can lead to an increase in the consumption of goods due to a higher household income.

Because of higher consumer goods demand, total waste generation and the in-use stock of will increase, putting potentially pressure on the environment if not properly recycled (refer to eqs. (A78)-(A81)). Therefore, while the initial goal of lowering the income tax was to foster the sharing economy and decrease the need for energy services produced at home, the policy could actually increase material and energy needs in the economy, although the effect can be ambiguous relying on the response of households to the policy and in return to the response of the production activities.

A.9.1.2.2 Lifestyle changes. Lifestyle changes in the willingness to participate in the sharing economy, through the implementation of educational programs, for example, directly impact the preference of households to consume sharing

services rather than producing at home energy services (refer to eq. (A6)). Also, the value of educational programs can lead to improved skills, widened access and use of enabling digital technologies, such as apps that facilitate the use of sharing services. This will impact the demand for durable goods and energy for the production of energy services at home (refer to eqs. (A7)-(A8)). In return, the demand addressed to the durable good firm will be potentially lower (refer to eqs. (A69), and (A26)-(A36)), decreasing the material and energy needed to produce durable goods. In the long run, municipal waste generation can be reduced due to a lower turnover rate for durable good stocks (refer to eqs. (A79) and (A81)). It can also lower industrial waste as the durable good firm would produce less in response to a lower demand (refer to eqs. (A78) and (A80)). In addition, in the long-term, there will be a reduction in the in-use stock of durable goods, as more durable goods will be shared and used more intensively instead of being used for the production of energy services at home. In view of the lower demand for energy for the production of durable goods, CO₂ emissions can be reduced.

The precedent results depend on the impact of an increase in revenues from sharing durable goods on households' consumption decisions. Increased participation in the sharing market will increase the demand for durable goods shared by a sharing firm (refer to eqs. (43)-(45)) and thus increase income. As a result, the use or investment of this additional income will have an impact on the overall income in terms of energy and materials needed to produce goods and waste generation. Indeed, the extra income received from the sharing economy (refer to eqs. (A2) and (A4)) could foster the production of goods other than durable goods. In addition, it could incentivize households to increase their durable good stock as it is profitable for them to buy durable goods and share them on a sharing platform thanks to a higher demand for sharing services. These results depend on the rate of use of durable goods. Overall, the initial expected negative impact on material and energy needs triggered by lifestyle changes could become positive in the long run.

A.9.1.3 Repair bonus, a favorable taxation, and lifestyle changes on repair services

CIRCEE's R4 to R5 strategies include the introduction of a bonus for repair services, a lower consumption tax for repairing services, and lifestyle changes to promote repair activities. It can help households to move towards a smarter use of products and a change in consumption practices.

Austria, France and Germany have implemented and tested repair bonuses (refer to [32] and [33]) with a view to promoting a higher repair rate for specific durable products. The European Commission, via its Right-to-Repair strategy for household appliances and cars, promotes the use of this instrument in addition to the implementation of repair funds among the Member States.

A repair bonus and a favorable on repair services will have a similar impact on consumption decision equations. Both economic instruments aim at reducing repair costs. The policy impacts eqs. (A14)-(A16). A lower price of repair relatively to the acquisition price of newly produced durable goods will favor the substitution toward repairing durable goods. This will foster the repairing sector at the expense of the durable good production sector. As a result, the demand for new durable goods decreases, resulting in a reduction in material and energy requirements in the durable goods sector (refer to eqs. (A69), and (A26)-(A36)). This will extend the lifetime of durable goods currently in use and slow the resource loop.

In the long run, since the demand for durable goods will be lower, this can decrease the total waste generated by the economy (refer to eqs. (A78)-(A81)). In the long term, the in-use stock of durable goods decreases (refer to eq. (A76)). However, a higher share of repaired durable goods in the total stock of durable goods of the economy can decrease at the aggregate level the level of fuel energy efficiency (refer to eq. (A10)), increasing the needs for energy.

In response to a lower demand for durable goods and higher demand for repair services, since the durable goods sector weighs more than the repair sector in terms of capital and labor input, the GDP can potentially decrease slightly. But this effect can be counterbalanced if a lower demand of durable goods means lower imports of durable goods and a lower trade deficit (refer to eqs. (A50)-(A51), and eq. (A53)). In addition, the decrease of material and energy needs from the durable goods sector will inevitably ameliorate the trade balance of the resource-poor economy as most resource needs are imported (refer to eqs. (A46)-(A49)).

The budget balance of the government may deteriorate if the repair bonus increases expenditure. In addition, as fewer durable goods are acquired and the taxation on repair services decreases, the government will have less revenues as less imports means less import tax revenues, less energy and material needs from the durable good firm means less industrial waste tax revenues and energy tax revenues and also less revenue from consumption tax revenues.

Lifestyle changes directly impact households' preference to consume repair services rather than buying new durable goods (refer to eq. (A15)). The effects on the economy are expected to be the same as fostering repair services from economic instruments, although of different magnitudes. There would be only a difference in the impact of public finances. Lifestyle changes, for example, through the implementation of an educational program will not result in higher public expenses because public expenditures on behavioral policies have not yet been included.

While these policies can effectively slow down the resource cycle, they may have a negative impact on GDP. The effect on CO₂ emissions will depend on whether the impact of increasing repair durable goods in the total stock of durable goods on energy needs will partially or totally offset the initial decrease of energy needs of the durable good and material producing firms. There is a possibility of trade-offs between slowing down the resource cycle and reducing CO₂ emissions and growth.

A.9.1.4 Higher import tariffs on material-intensive goods

An increase in import tariffs for material-intensive goods is part of CIRCEE R0 to R2.

The strategy impacts the demand for import goods (refer to eqs. (A50)-(A51)) and the price of goods $p_{g,t}$, that is an aggregate price of the final price of imports and the final price of goods produced domestically. An increase in import tariffs will reduce the demand for imported goods, which may be more material intensive than domestic products. This can decrease municipal waste generation (refer to eqs. (A79) and (A81)). The total in-use stock will be lower in the long-run because the demand will shift toward domestic goods which can be potentially produced at a lower material intensity (refer to eqs. (A73)-(A76)). However, a shift toward domestic production increases the domestic economy's material and energy needs to produce goods that were originally imported (equations (A29)-(A36)). Energy consumption, industrial waste, and CO2 emissions can therefore increase at the country level.

Decreasing imports could ameliorate the trade balance (refer to eq. (A53)), foster domestic production, and positively impact GDP. However, the initial positive effect of decreasing imports on the trade balance could be partially or totally erased by the need for more energy and materials to produce domestic good. As a result, income would increase, leading to increased consumption, and there would also be a need for higher materials and energy in order to address higher demands. As a result, an increase in the import tariff reduces municipal waste generated in the economy, it could lead to a higher production of industrial waste caused by higher domestic production. A regionalized model would be needed to assess if the policy, reducing the demand for goods in countries where the resource productivity is, negatively or positively impacts CO2 emissions and resource use at the global level.

The effect on public finances is not clear and will depend on how households react to changes in the relative prices of goods and a potential higher income. This may offset the initial negative impact of the reduction of import tariff revenues (see eq. (A59)).

A.9.1.5 Municipal waste tax

The waste tax policy is embedded in strategies R0 to R1. The aim is to reduce waste generation by reducing the consumption of certain goods.

An increase in the waste tax can have a negative impact on the budget constraint of households (refer to eqs. (A2) and (A4)) and have a negative impact on the total cost of non-durable and semi-durable products. The waste tax is not applied to durable goods because an EPR scheme is already in place and the municipal waste tax only applies to specific goods in Japan. Since non-energy services costs increase, households can substitute energy services (refer to eq. (A5)). The substitution can foster higher durable good acquisition and higher energy needs to produce energy services at home and to address the higher demand of sharing services (see eqs. (A6) and (A7)). In the short run, this will decrease municipal waste generation because of a lower demand for non-durable goods that are disposed as soon as they are consumed, but it could increase in the long-run municipal waste generation in response to a higher demand for durable goods (refer to eqs. (A79) and (A81)). Indeed, depending on the magnitude of the response of semi-durable goods and durable goods consumption decisions, more materials could be added to total in-use stock (refer to eqs. (A73)-(A77)) giving rise to higher waste generation in the long run.

As a result of an initial increase in the waste tax, households may move away from the consumption of non-durable and semi-durable goods, thereby reducing the demand directed to production firms (refer to eqs. (A29)-(A36)). A decrease in the production of non-durable and semi-durable goods decreases the firm's material and energy needs, thereby decreasing waste generation during the production process (refer to eqs. (A78) and (A80)). A lower demand for resources can improve the balance of trade in the economy. However, there is ambiguity as to the effect on GDP. While the durable goods sector, the sharing sector and potentially the repairing sector can be fostered in response of a higher demand of energy services, the non-durable and semi-durable goods sectors will be potentially negatively impacted by the increase of the municipal waste tax.

The impact on CO2 emissions will also depend on whether there is a high or moderate substitution of non-durable goods and semi-durable goods with energy services. A low or moderate substitution can potentially decrease CO2 emissions at the country level thanks to lower material and energy needs for the production of non-durable and semi-durable goods. However, a high substitution can potentially offset and even increase the CO2 emissions of the economy because of higher energy needs from the consumption of energy services and the production of sharing services (refer to eqs. (A43)-(A45)).

Finally, the impact on public finances is also ambiguous and will depend highly on the response of households to the implementation of the waste tax. While higher revenues from the taxation of municipal waste can improve public finances, lower revenues from the taxation of non-durable and semi-durable consumption will have a negative impact on public finances.

A.9.2 CE strategy implementation in firms' equations

Strategies R2 and R8 directly impact firm production decisions. The list of instruments used to foster sustainable production practices are given in [A3](#).

Table A3: Circular Economy Strategies in CIRCEE

Potting et al. (2017)	Goal in CIRCEE LIFE	Instruments in CIRCEE LIFE
R2 : Reduce	Reduce the use of materials in goods and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shock on the material productivity • Waste tax • Material substitution
R8 : Recycle	Useful application of materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste tax • Subsidies to recycling firms • Price differential between primary and secondary materials

A.9.2.1 Industrial waste tax

The increase in the industrial waste tax on landfilled waste is embedded in the strategy R8 and R2.

Relying on the level of substitutability of materials, the tax can incentivize producers to increase their demand for secondary materials and reduce the amount of resources used in production processes (refer to eqs. (A29) to (A36)). A lower demand for materials leads to a more sustainable production process, thereby reducing potential industrial waste (refer to eqs. (A78) and (A80)) and potentially helping the economy to narrow the resource cycle. As the model set up is in perfect foresight, there is no inflation in the model meaning that the inputs in the production process are the ones making the adjustments in response to shocks. In view of the fact that production processes will become less resource-intensive, the energy needs for the production of materials will also decrease (refer to eqs. (A19) and (A25)). In response to a lower use of materials in production processes, a firm is able to increase capital- and labor-intensive production processes, thereby promoting growth. However, if production processes become more capital intensive, the capital in-use stock will be increased (refer to eq. (A77)) and the energy needed to produce capital goods will increase. On the other hand, a more capital-intensive economy will increase the generation of future waste from capital goods (refer to eqs. (A78) and (A80)). As a result, there is ambiguity as to the overall impact of an increase in landfilled industrial waste tax on CO2 emissions and industrial waste disposal and needs to be examined.

In addition, a higher industrial landfill waste tax could increase government revenues from waste taxation in the short term (refer to eq. (A59)). In the long-term, if production processes are transformed into more capital-intensive and labor-intensive processes, public finances will also have a positive impact, as public revenue from capital and labor taxes will increase. In addition, as final good firms demand less materials to produce goods, the import of materials will decrease, thus improving the trade balance of the economy (refer to eq. (A53)), thereby potentially increasing GDP.

A.9.2.2 Subsidies to the recycling firm

The CIRCEE R8 strategy incorporates public subsidies to recycling firms. The strategy focuses primarily on reducing the potential profit losses of the recycling firm (refer to eq. (A21) and (A23)) as a result of the high marginal costs. Subsidies are covered by the government's budget (refer to eq. (A60)). High subsidies can negatively impact public finances although the impact will be relatively low because of the relative weight of subsidies in total public expenses.

A.9.2.3 Shock on material productivity and recycling quality

This strategy is included in R2 and R8 in order to help the economy narrow down and partially close resource loops in the economy. In its current version, CIRCEE does not contain endogenous technical changes which could affect the productivity of the economy or the quality of the recycling of goods, which would have an impact on the price difference between primary and secondary material. CIRCEE will include endogenous recycling quality and endogenous material productivity in a future version.

CIRCEE adjust the value of the material productivity of production processes (refer to eqs. (A30)). Increased material productivity reduces the quantity of materials needed for the production of goods. This will have a positive impact on the trade balance as less materials are imported (refer to eq. (A46)), on industrial waste generation as less materials are lost during the production process of goods (refer to eqs. (A78) and (A80)), and on the total in-use stock (refer to eqs. (A73)-(A77)) as goods become lighter. In addition, a decrease in material needs can potentially reduce the demand for materials for material processing firms and recycling firms, thereby reducing the economy's energy requirements. Overall, the strategy can help the economy narrow the resource loop.

On the consumption side, lighter goods reduce municipal waste generation (refer to eqs. (A79) and (A81)) and improve households' income (refer to eqs. (A2) and (A4)) through lower municipal tax expenditures. The extra-income can be used to consume more goods. Due to the low municipal waste tax rate, the impact on households' consumption is potentially negligible. There could be a positive impact on GDP owing to a slight increase in consumption and improvement of trade balance.

The impact on public revenue (refer to eq. (A59)) is potentially negative due to a reduction in industrial and municipal waste taxes. However, it is possible to partially offset this impact by higher household consumption, resulting in higher VAT revenue.

A.9.2.4 Price differentials in primary and secondary materials

CIRCEE can also adjust the prices of primary and secondary materials. In order to allow the economy to partially close the resource loop, secondary material prices can be exogenously reduced (as they are fixed on global material markets) compared to primary materials prices.

The shock will impact the material mix of final goods producing firms (refer to eqs. (A30)-(A33)) in favor of secondary materials fostering the recycling activity. In view of the fact that more recycled material is produced within the economy, less primary materials are imported. The impact on the trade balance can be potentially positive, although it will depend on whether the economy decides to increase the domestic production of secondary materials rather than importing secondary materials from abroad (refer to eqs. (A46)-(A49)). The impact on energy needs depends on the energy intensity of the material processing firm and the recycling activity (eqs. (A21) and (A25)), there will be a negative impact on CO₂ emissions due to higher energy demand.

Appendix B Model's calibration

The model parameters and exogenous variables are calibrated using Japanese national statistics (E-stat and the Agency of Natural Resources and Energy), the Japan Industrial Productivity Database 2021 from RIETI, the GLORIA database from [34] and [35], OECD.stat database, literature studies, SSP database ([36], [37], [38]), online surveys and expert consensus approaches (refer to Tables B7 and B8). The base year of the model is 2018.

The distribution parameters of the Constant Elasticity Substitution (CES) consumption and production function are carefully computed from the first order conditions of the model and data à la [39] to avoid any dimension problem (see Table 2). The consumption and production structures of the model are based on Constant Elasticity Substitution (CES) functions. CES functions fail to verify dimension homogeneity due to variations in units of measurement between production inputs (i.e., capital measured in different units than labor) as pointed out by [40]. Additionally, the distribution parameters of CES functions are contingent upon the substitution elasticity. Using non-normalized production functions not only obscures calibration results but also impacts the dynamic responses to shocks, as the output elasticity with respect to production inputs can differ across different steady states. To address these issues, the distribution parameters of the model are re-parameterized à la [40]. The substitution parameters are calibrated from the literature and the WITCH model. A future version of the model will estimate directly from the data the substitution parameters.

Parameters and exogenous variables related to materials are calibrated on the model's first order conditions and/or on data from the GLORIA database (commodity prices), Resource Panel's Global Material Flow database (trade of materials, DMC and DMI), RIETI's input-output tables and the Ministry of the Environment (waste generation and management). The material needs of each sector for the base year were computed in a combination of commodity price data from GLORIA, materials expenses from RIETI's input-output tables, waste generation data and Sankey Diagrams from the Ministry of the Environment, and DMC and trade data from Resource Panel.

Parameters and exogenous variables related to waste were calibrated on the model's first order conditions and on detailed reports and surveys from the Ministry of the Environment on waste management in Japan.

Extended Producer Responsibility (collection, transportation and recycling) fees were reported by data provided by the Ministry of Economy and, and Industry and [41]. To compute the EPR fees as a share of the final price of durable goods, we did a weighted average of the share of the main energy-using durable goods in total consumption expenses and average price of these appliances from the Japan Electrical Manufacturer's Association reports, online retailers (next-drive.com) and surveys (city-costs.com).

Energy prices and taxes are calibrated for the base year from the Agency of Natural Resources and Energy, and OECD.stat data. The evolution of electricity prices and fuel prices follow the same as in the WITCH model. The evolution of energy efficiency for electricity and non-electrical energy is based in WITCH data.

The model is detrended by labor-productivity and demographic growth and normalized by the Gross Domestic Product.

References

- [1] King, R.G., Plosser, C.I., Rebelo, S.T.: Production, growth and business cycles: I. the basic neoclassical model. *Journal of monetary Economics* **21**(2-3), 195–232 (1988)
- [2] Benjaafar, S., Kong, G., Li, X., Courcoubetis, C.: Peer-to-peer product sharing: Implications for ownership, usage, and social welfare in the sharing economy. *Management Science* **65**(2), 477–493 (2019)
- [3] André, F.J., Arguedas, C., Rousseau, S.: Strategic pricing, lifespan choices and environmental implications of peer-to-peer sharing. In: EAERE-Conference of the European Association of Environmental and Resource Economists-2021/06/24, Location: Berlin, Germany (online) (2021)
- [4] Fraiberger, S.P., Sundararajan, A.: Peer-to-peer rental markets in the sharing economy. NYU Stern School of Business Research Paper (First version March 2015 (2017)

- [5] Ogaki, M., Reinhart, C.M.: Measuring intertemporal substitution: The role of durable goods. *Journal of political Economy* **106**(5), 1078–1098 (1998)
- [6] Marsiliani, L., Renstrom, T.I.: Time inconsistency in environmental policy: tax earmarking as a commitment solution. *The Economic Journal* **110**(462), 123–138 (2000)
- [7] Dhawan, R., Jeske, K.: Energy price shocks and the macroeconomy: the role of consumer durables. *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking* **40**(7), 1357–1377 (2008)
- [8] Becker, G.S.: A theory of the allocation of time. *The economic journal* **75**(299), 493–517 (1965)
- [9] Lancaster, K.J.: A new approach to consumer theory. *Journal of political economy* **74**(2), 132–157 (1966)
- [10] Muth, R.F.: Household production and consumer demand functions. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*, 699–708 (1966)
- [11] Gutowski, T.G., Sahni, S., Boustani, A., Graves, S.C.: Remanufacturing and energy savings. *Environmental science & technology* **45**(10), 4540–4547 (2011)
- [12] Ordóñez-de-Haro, J.M., Torres, J.L., et al.: Sharing economy in macroeconomics: Collaborative consumption and durable goods. Technical report (2019)
- [13] Pettifor, H., Wilson, C., Agnew, M.: A universal framework for measuring and modelling low-carbon lifestyles. *Global Environmental Change* **forthcoming** (2023)
- [14] Christiano, L.J., Eichenbaum, M., Evans, C.L.: Nominal rigidities and the dynamic effects of a shock to monetary policy. *Journal of political Economy* **113**(1), 1–45 (2005)
- [15] Lafforgue, G., Rouge, L.: A dynamic model of recycling with endogenous technological breakthrough. *Resource and Energy Economics* **57**, 101–118 (2019)
- [16] García-Barragán, J.F., Eyckmans, J., Rousseau, S.: Defining and measuring the circular economy: a mathematical approach. *Ecological Economics* **157**, 369–372 (2019)
- [17] Grüning, P., Banionienė, J., Dagilienė, L., Donadelli, M., Jüppner, M., Kizys, R., Lessmann, K., et al.: The quadrilemma of a small open circular economy through a prism of the 9r strategies. Technical report, Bank of Lithuania (2021)
- [18] André, F.J., Arguedas, C., Rousseau, S.: Strategic pricing, lifespan choices and environmental implications of peer-to-peer sharing. In: EAERE-Conference of the European Association of Environmental and Resource Economists-2021/06/24, Location: Berlin, Germany (online) (2021)
- [19] Lahcen, B., Eyckmans, J., Rousseau, S., Dams, Y., Brusselaers, J.: Modelling the circular economy: Introducing a supply chain equilibrium approach. *Ecological Economics* **197**, 107451 (2022)
- [20] Skelton, A.C., Paroussos, L., Allwood, J.M.: Comparing energy and material efficiency rebound effects: an exploration of scenarios in the gem-e3 macroeconomic model. *Ecological Economics* **173**, 106544 (2020)
- [21] Dasgupta, P., Heal, G.: The optimal depletion of exhaustible resources. *The review of economic studies* **41**(5), 3–28 (1974)
- [22] Anderson, C.L.: The production process: Inputs and wastes. *Journal of environmental economics and management* **14**(1), 1–12 (1987)
- [23] Mensbrugge, D., Peters, J.C.: Volume preserving ces and cet formulations (2020)
- [24] Albonico, A., Cales, L., Cardani, R., Croitorov, O., Ferroni, F., Giovannini, M., Hohberger, S., Pataracchia, B., Pericoli, F., Raciborski, R., et al.: The Global Multi-country Model (GM): an Estimated DSGE Model for the Euro Area Countries vol. 2017/10. JRC Working Papers in Economics and Finance, ??? (2017)
- [25] McGrattan, E.R., Rogerson, R., Wright, R.: An equilibrium model of the business cycle with household production and fiscal policy. *International Economic Review*, 267–290 (1997)
- [26] Leeper, E.M.: Equilibria under ‘active’and ‘passive’monetary and fiscal policies. *Journal of monetary Economics*

27(1), 129–147 (1991)

- [27] Fauvel, Y., Samson, L.: Intertemporal substitution and durable goods: an empirical analysis. *Canadian Journal of Economics*, 192–205 (1991)
- [28] Lanteri, A.: The market for used capital: Endogenous irreversibility and reallocation over the business cycle. *American Economic Review* **108**(9), 2383–2419 (2018)
- [29] Barro, R.J.: Government spending in a simple model of endogeneous growth. *Journal of political economy* **98**(5, Part 2), 103–125 (1990)
- [30] Glomm, G., Ravikumar, B.: Public investment in infrastructure in a simple growth model. *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control* **18**(6), 1173–1187 (1994)
- [31] Cassou, S.P., Lansing, K.J.: Optimal fiscal policy, public capital, and the productivity slowdown. *Journal of economic dynamics and control* **22**(6), 911–935 (1998)
- [32] Repair.eu: Germany and austria implement repair bonuses (2021)
- [33] Transition Ecologique, M.: Le bonus réparation, qu’est-ce-que c’est ? (2024)
- [34] Lenzen, M., Geschke, A., Abd Rahman, M.D., Xiao, Y., Fry, J., Reyes, R., Dietzenbacher, E., Inomata, S., Kanemoto, K., Los, B., *et al.*: The global mrio lab—charting the world economy. *Economic Systems Research* **29**(2), 158–186 (2017)
- [35] Lenzen, M., Geschke, A., West, J., Fry, J., Malik, A., Giljum, S., Canals, L., Piñero, P., Lutter, S., Wiedmann, T., *et al.*: Implementing the material footprint to measure progress towards sustainable development goals 8 and 12. *Nature Sustainability* **5**(2), 157–166 (2022)
- [36] Riahi, K., Vuuren, D.P., Kriegler, E., Edmonds, J., O’Neill, B.C., Fujimori, S., Bauer, N., Calvin, K., Dellink, R., Fricko, O., Lutz, W., Popp, A., Cuaresma, J.C., KC, S., Leimbach, M., Jiang, L., Kram, T., Rao, S., Emmerling, J., Ebi, K., Hasegawa, T., Havlik, P., HumpenÄ¶nder, F., Silva, L.A.D., Smith, S., Stehfest, E., Bosetti, V., Eom, J., Gernaat, D., Masui, T., Rogelj, J., Strefler, J., Drouet, L., Krey, V., Luderer, G., Harmsen, M., Takahashi, K., Baumstark, L., Doelman, J.C., Kainuma, M., Klimont, Z., Marangoni, G., Lotze-Campen, H., Obersteiner, M., Tabeau, A., Tavoni, M.: The shared socioeconomic pathways and their energy, land use, and greenhouse gas emissions implications: An overview. *Global Environmental Change* **42**, 153–168 (2017) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2016.05.009>
- [37] Rogelj, J., Popp, A., Calvin, K.V., Luderer, G., Emmerling, J., Gernaat, D., Fujimori, S., Strefler, J., Hasegawa, T., Marangoni, G., Krey, V., Kriegler, E., Riahi, K., Vuuren, D.P., Doelman, J., Drouet, L., Edmonds, J., Fricko, O., Harmsen, M., Havlík, P., HumpenÄ¶nder, F., Stehfest, E., Tavoni, M.: Scenarios towards limiting global mean temperature increase below 1.5 °c. *Nature Climate Change* **8**(4), 325–332 (2018) <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-018-0091-3>
- [38] Gidden, M.J., Riahi, K., Smith, S.J., Fujimori, S., Luderer, G., Kriegler, E., Vuuren, D.P., Berg, M., Feng, L., Klein, D., Calvin, K., Doelman, J.C., Frank, S., Fricko, O., Harmsen, M., Hasegawa, T., Havlik, P., Hilaire, J., Hoesly, R., Horing, J., Popp, A., Stehfest, E., Takahashi, K.: Global emissions pathways under different socioeconomic scenarios for use in cmip6: a dataset of harmonized emissions trajectories through the end of the century. *Geoscientific Model Development* **12**(4), 1443–1475 (2019) <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-1443-2019>
- [39] Cantore, C., Levine, P.: Getting normalization right: Dealing with ‘dimensional constants’ in macroeconomics. *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control* **36**(12), 1931–1949 (2012)
- [40] Cantore, C., Levine, P.: Getting normalization right: Dealing with ‘dimensional constants’ in macroeconomics. *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control* **36**(12), 1931–1949 (2012)
- [41] Hotta, Y., Aoki-Suzuki, C.: Waste reduction and recycling initiatives in japanese cities: Lessons from yokohama and kamakura. *Waste Management & Research* **32**(9), 857–866 (2014)
- [42] Feenstra, R.C., Luck, P., Obstfeld, M., Russ, K.N.: In search of the armington elasticity. *Review of Economics and Statistics* **100**(1), 135–150 (2018)
- [43] Bajzik, J., Havranek, T., Irsova, Z., Schwarz, J.: Estimating the armington elasticity: The importance of study

- design and publication bias. *Journal of International Economics* **127**, 103383 (2020)
- [44] Corbier, D., Gonand, F.: A hybrid electricity-economy model to assess the aggregate impacts of low-carbon transition: An application to france. *Ecological Economics* **216**, 108027 (2024)
- [45] Dhawan, R., Jeske, K.: Energy price shocks and the macroeconomy: the role of consumer durables. *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking* **40**(7), 1357–1377 (2008)
- [46] Henriët, F., Maggiar, N., Schubert, K.: A stylized applied energy-economy model for france. *The Energy Journal* **35**(4), 1–38 (2014)
- [47] Corbier, D., Gonand, F.: The aggregate effects of the structure of information in low-carbon transition policies: An application to france. *Energy and Climate Change* **4**, 100115 (2023)
- [48] Capros, P., Van Regemorter, D., Paroussos, L., Karkatsoulis, P., Fragkiadakis, C., Tsani, S., Charalampidis, I., Revesz, T., Perry, M., Abrell, J.: Gem-e3 model documentation. *JRC Scientific and Policy Reports* **26034** (2013)
- [49] Okagawa, A., Kanemi, B., et al.: Estimation of substitution elasticities for cge models. Technical report (2008)
- [50] Mućk, J., et al.: Elasticity of Substitution Between Labor and Capital: Robust Evidence from Developed Economies. Narodowy Bank Polski. Education & Publishing Department, ??? (2017)
- [51] Emmerling, J., Drouet, L., Reis, L., Bevione, M., Berger, L., Bosetti, V., Carrara, S., De Cian, E., De Maere D’Aertrycke, G., Longden, T., et al.: The witch 2016 model-documentation and implementation of the shared socioeconomic pathways (2016)
- [52] Wang, F., Jiang, Y., Zhang, W., Yang, F.: Elasticity of factor substitution and driving factors of energy intensity in china’s industry. *Energy & Environment* **30**(3), 385–407 (2019)
- [53] Burniaux, J.-M., Truong, T.P.: Gtap-e: an energy-environmental version of the gtap model. *GTAP technical papers*, 18 (2002)
- [54] Iiboshi, H., Matsumae, T., Namba, R., Nishiyama, S.-I.: Estimating a dsge model for japan in a data-rich environment. *Journal of the Japanese and International Economies* **36**, 25–55 (2015)
- [55] Sugo, T., Ueda, K.: Estimating a dynamic stochastic general equilibrium model for japan. *Journal of the Japanese and International Economies* **22**(4), 476–502 (2008)
- [56] Hansen, L.P., Singleton, K.J.: Generalized instrumental variables estimation of nonlinear rational expectations models. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*, 1269–1286 (1982)
- [57] Lanteri, A.: The market for used capital: Endogenous irreversibility and reallocation over the business cycle. *American Economic Review* **108**(9), 2383–2419 (2018)
- [58] Melina, G., Cantelmo, A.: Sectoral labor mobility and optimal monetary policy. Technical report, International Monetary Fund (2017)
- [59] Havranek, T., Rusnak, M., Sokolova, A.: Habit formation in consumption: A meta-analysis. *European Economic Review* **95**, 142–167 (2017)
- [60] Deetman, S., Pauliuk, S., Van Vuuren, D.P., Van Der Voet, E., Tukker, A.: Scenarios for demand growth of metals in electricity generation technologies, cars, and electronic appliances. *Environmental science & technology* **52**(8), 4950–4959 (2018)
- [61] Nakamoto, Y., Kagawa, S.: A generalized framework for analyzing car lifetime effects on stock, flow, and carbon footprint. *Journal of Industrial Ecology* **26**(2), 433–447 (2022)
- [62] Nomura, K., Suga, Y.: Measurement of depreciation rates using microdata from disposal survey of japan. In: *The 35th IARIW General Conference*, Copenhagen, Denmark (2018)
- [63] Heatmap.news: How tokyo became an anti-car paradise. access at <https://heatmap.news/economy/tokyo-anti-car-pedestrian-paradise>: :text=Car(2023)
- [64] prtimes.jp: Survey on washing machines: 40access at <https://prtimes.jp/main/html/rd/p/000001061.000007815.html>

(2021)

- [65] whatjapanthinks.com: Japanese air-conditioners usage. access at <https://whatjapanthinks.com/2007/05/30/japanese-air-conditioner-usage/> (2007)
- [66] tg-uchi.jp: More than half of people wash their clothes every day! how often does everyone wash their clothes? access at <https://tg-uchi.jp/topics/5946> (2023)
- [67] datareportal.com: The unique nuances of digital in japan. access at <https://datareportal.com/reports/the-unique-nuances-of-digital-in-japan> (2021)
- [68] travelvoice.jp: The average time spending for a smart phone in japan is 3 hours and 7 minutes a user a day. access at <https://www.travelvoice.jp/english/the-average-time-spending-for-a-smart-phone-in-japan-is-3-hours-and-7-minutes-a-user-a-day> (2018)
- [69] Tasaki, T., Motoshita, M., Uchida, H., Suzuki, Y.: Assessing the replacement of electrical home appliances for the environment: an aid to consumer decision making. *Journal of Industrial Ecology* **17**(2), 290–298 (2013)
- [70] Hotta, Y., Hayashi, S., Bengtsson, M., Mori, H.: ‘extended producer responsibility policy in east asia. Consideration of International Resource Circulation (2009)
- [71] octorate.com: Frais airbnb : combien airbnb prend de commission (2023)
- [72] Newlands, G., Lutz, C., Fieseler, C.: Navigating peer-to-peer pricing in the sharing economy. Available at SSRN 3116954 (2018)
- [73] yamamoto-mrc.co.jp: What is industrial waste tax? a thorough explanation of the tax system. access at <https://www.yamamoto-mrc.co.jp/column/industrial/>(2021)

Parameter	Description	Unit	Value	Source of data
g	labor-productivity growth rate	-	0.011678	SSPs database ([36], [37], [38])
n	population growth rate	-	-0.0064	SSPs database ([36], [37], [38])
$\sigma^{imports}$	import Armington elasticity	-	3.4	[42] and [43]
$\sigma^{exports}$	export Armington elasticity	-	3.1	[42] and [43]
σ^c	non-energy services and energy services substitution elasticity	-	0.98	[5] and [44]
σ^{home}	durable goods and energy substitution elasticity	-	0.425	[45], [46] and [47]
σ	capital-labor-energy and material inputs substitution elasticity	-	0.2	[48] and [49]
σ^{kl}	capital and labor inputs substitution elasticity	-	0.75	[50] and [49]
σ^e	firms' electricity and fuels inputs substitution elasticity	-	0.66	WITCH model [51]
σ^m	primary and secondary material inputs substitution elasticity	-	0.8	Model's assumption
σ^{es}	home-produced and shared energy services substitution elasticity	-	1.25	WITCH model [51]
σ^{le}	capital-labor and energy inputs substitution elasticity	-	0.66	Model's assumption
σ^{share}	households' electricity and fuels substitution elasticity	-	0.4	WITCH model [51]
σ^{tes}	sharing firm's labor input and durable good-energy inputs substitution elasticity	-	0.5	Model's assumption
σ^{nes}	intertemporal elasticity of substitution	-	1.22	[54] and [55]
$\sigma^{inv,d}$	non-durable good and semi-durable good substitution elasticity	-	0.98	[56], [27] and [5]
$\theta^{durable}$	repair and new durable goods substitution elasticity	-	5	Model's assumption and [57]
$\theta^{capital}$	durable goods investment adjustment cost parameter	-	0.86845	[58]
τ^{vat}	capital goods investment adjustment cost parameter	-	1.46	[58]
τ^k	V.A.T. tax	-	0.092	OECD.stat and RIETI
τ^l	capital income tax	-	0.18274	OECD.stat and RIETI
τ^r	labor income tax	-	0.31957	OECD.stat and RIETI
$share^{non-durable}$	government's non-durable good demand share of non-durable good production	-	0.31738	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$share^{semi-durable}$	government's semi-durable good demand share of semi-durable good production	-	0.00017	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$share^{durable}$	government's durable good demand share of durable good production	-	0.00001	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha^{non-durable}$	non-durable good producing firm's labor distribution parameter	-	0.037464	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha^{non-durable}$	non-durable good producing firm's capital distribution parameter	-	0.58487	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha^{semi-durable}$	semi-durable good producing firm's labor distribution parameter	-	0.04304	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha^{semi-durable}$	semi-durable good producing firm's capital distribution parameter	-	0.45807	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha^{durable}$	durable good producing firm's labor distribution parameter	-	0.02553	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha^{durable}$	durable good producing firm's capital distribution parameter	-	0.90003	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha^{capital}$	capital good producing firm's labor distribution parameter	-	0.02550	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha^{capital}$	capital good producing firm's capital distribution parameter	-	0.90101	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
α^{prim}	primary material producing firm's labor distribution parameter	-	0.040178	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
α^{prim}	primary material producing firm's capital distribution parameter	-	0.52165	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
α^{secd}	secondary material producing firm's labor distribution parameter	-	0.02874	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
α^{secd}	secondary material producing firm's capital distribution parameter	-	0.80890	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
α^{repair}	repair firm's labor distribution parameter	-	0.06480	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI and OECD data
α^{repair}	repair firm's capital distribution parameter	-	0.07953	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI and OECD data
$\alpha^{kl,repair}$	non-durable good producing firm's capital-labor distribution parameter	-	0.85993	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha^{e,non-durable}$	non-durable good producing firm's energy distribution parameter	-	0.00016	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy and RIETI data

Table B4: Calibration of CIRCEE

Parameter	Description	Unit	Value	Source of data
$\alpha_{kl}^{semi-durable}$	semi-durable good producing firm's capital-labor distribution parameter	-	0.85091	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{en}^{semi-durable}$	semi-durable good producing firm's energy distribution parameter	-	0.00012	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, and RIETI data
$\alpha_{dl}^{durable}$	durable good producing firm's capital-labor distribution parameter	-	0.92383	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{de}^{durable}$	durable good producing firm's energy distribution parameter	-	0.00002	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{cl}^{capital}$	capital good producing firm's capital-labor distribution parameter	-	0.96116	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
α_c^e	capital good producing firm's energy distribution parameter	-	4.33e-06	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, and RIETI data
$\alpha_{kl}^{capital}$	primary material producing firm's capital-labor distribution parameter	-	0.44803	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{em}^{primary}$	primary material producing firm's energy distribution parameter	-	0.00755	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{kl}^{secondary}$	secondary material producing firm's capital-labor distribution parameter	-	0.68806	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{em}^{secondary}$	secondary material producing firm's energy distribution parameter	-	0.00089	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{kl}^{non-durable}$	non-durable good producing firm's capital-labor-energy distribution parameter	-	0.89176	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{em}^{non-durable}$	non-durable good producing firm's material distribution parameter	-	0.00193	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{kl}^{semi-durable}$	semi-durable good producing firm's capital-labor-energy distribution parameter	-	0.32117	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{em}^{semi-durable}$	semi-durable good producing firm's material distribution parameter	-	11.4182	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI data, Ministry of the Environment's data, Resource Panel database, GLORIA database of [34] and [35]
$\alpha_{kl}^{durable}$	durable good producing firm's capital-labor-energy distribution parameter	-	0.45841	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{em}^{durable}$	durable good producing firm's material distribution parameter	-	20.7540	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI data, Ministry of the Environment's data, Resource Panel database, GLORIA database of [34] and [35]
$\alpha_{kl}^{capital}$	capital good producing firm's capital-labor-energy distribution parameter	-	0.40783	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{em}^{capital}$	capital good producing firm's material distribution parameter	-	35.800	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI data, Ministry of the Environment's data, Resource Panel database, GLORIA database of [34] and [35]
$\alpha_{kl}^{primary}$	primary material producing firm's capital-labor-energy distribution parameter	-	1.264e-06	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{em}^{primary}$	primary material producing firm's raw material distribution parameter	-	0.15357	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI data, Ministry of the Environment's data, Resource Panel database, GLORIA database of [34] and [35]
$\alpha_{kl}^{secondary}$	secondary material producing firm's capital-labor-energy distribution parameter	-	7.573e-06	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{em}^{secondary}$	secondary material producing firm's recyclable waste distribution parameter	-	0.00205	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI data, Ministry of the Environment's data, Resource Panel database, GLORIA database of [34] and [35]
β	discount factor	-	0.98685	Model's First Order Conditions
$\alpha_{domestic}^{domestic}$	domestic production of non-durable good distribution parameter	-	1.03362	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{domestic}^{semi-durable}$	domestic production of semi-durable good distribution parameter	-	0.48613	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{domestic}^{durable}$	domestic production of durable good distribution parameter	-	0.73690	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{domestic}^{capital}$	domestic production of capital good distribution parameter	-	0.85038	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{domestic}^{primary}$	domestic production of primary material distribution parameter	-	0.95261	Model's First Order Conditions, Resource Panel and RIETI data
$\alpha_{domestic}^{secondary}$	domestic production of secondary material distribution parameter	-	0.95261	Model's First Order Conditions, Ministry of the Environment, Resource Panel and RIETI data
$\alpha_{imp}^{non-durable}$	imports of non-durable good distribution parameter	-	0.55996	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{imp}^{semi-durable}$	imports of semi-durable good distribution parameter	-	0.48618	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{imp}^{durable}$	imports of durable good distribution parameter	-	0.87934	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{imp}^{capital}$	imports of capital good distribution parameter	-	0.52275	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
$\alpha_{imp}^{primary}$	imports of primary material distribution parameter	-	0.57479	Model's First Order Conditions, Resource Panel and RIETI data
$\alpha_{imp}^{secondary}$	imports of secondary material distribution parameter	-	0.57479	Model's First Order Conditions, Ministry of the Environment, Resource Panel and RIETI data
$\alpha_{exp}^{non-durable}$	exports of non-durable good to the Rest of the World (RoW) distribution parameter	-	0.23345	Model's First Order Conditions, World Bank and RIETI data
$\alpha_{exp}^{semi-durable}$	exports of semi-durable good to the RoW distribution parameter	-	0.34285	Model's First Order Conditions, World Bank and RIETI data
$\alpha_{exp}^{durable}$	exports of durable good to the RoW distribution parameter	-	0.36917	Model's First Order Conditions, World Bank and RIETI data
$\alpha_{exp}^{capital}$	exports of capital good to the RoW distribution parameter	-	0.27899	Model's First Order Conditions, World Bank and RIETI data
$\alpha_{exp}^{primary}$	exports of primary materials to the RoW distribution parameter	-	1.01682	Model's First Order Conditions, Resource Panel and RIETI data

Table B5: Calibration of CIRCEE (continued)

Parameter	Description	Unit	Value	Source of data
α_{env}^{sec}	exports of secondary materials to the RoW distribution parameter	-	1.02749	Model's First Order Conditions, Ministry of the Environment, Resource Panel and RIETI data
$\alpha_{foreign}^{ndurable}$	foreign production of non-durable good distribution parameter	-	0.99689	Model's First Order Conditions, WorldBank and RIETI data
$\alpha_{semdurable}^{ndurable}$	foreign production of semi-durable good distribution parameter	-	0.98817	Model's First Order Conditions, WorldBank and RIETI data
$\alpha_{foreign}^{durable}$	foreign production of durable good distribution parameter	-	0.98508	Model's First Order Conditions, WorldBank and RIETI data
$\alpha_{capital}^{durable}$	foreign production of capital good distribution parameter	-	0.99379	Model's First Order Conditions, WorldBank and RIETI data
$Demand_{foreign}^{ndurable}$	Foreign demand for the domestic production of capital goods	-	12.3356	World Bank and RIETI data
$Demand_{foreign}^{durable}$	Foreign demand for the domestic production of semi-durable goods	-	12.3356	World Bank and RIETI data
$Demand_{foreign}^{semdurable}$	Foreign demand for the domestic production of non-durable goods	-	12.3356	World Bank and RIETI data
$Demand_{capital}^{semdurable}$	Foreign demand for the domestic production of durable goods	-	10.91000	World Bank and RIETI data
T^Y	Social transfers	JPY	0.12465	OECD data
$h_{lowcarbon}$	Lowcarbon household's habit consumption parameter	-	0.55	[59]
$h_{cautious}$	Cautious household's habit consumption parameter	-	0.55	[59]
h_{constr}	Constrained household's habit consumption parameter	-	0.55	[59]
α_{share}^{e}	sharing firm's durable good input distribution parameter	-	1.49506	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI and OECD data
α_{share}^{e*}	sharing firm's energy input distribution parameter	-	0.03825	Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, E-stat, OECD and RIETI databases
α_{share}^{e**}	sharing firm's energy services input distribution parameter	-	0.44035	Model's First Order Conditions
α_{share}^{e***}	sharing firm's labor input parameter	-	0.00004	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
α_{es}^{e}	non-energy services distribution parameter	-	0.87823	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
α_{es}^{e*}	energy services distribution parameter	-	0.11441	Model's First Order Conditions
α_{es}^{e**}	non-durable goods distribution parameter	-	0.91262	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
α_{es}^{e***}	semi-durable goods distribution parameter	-	0.08384	Model's First Order Conditions and RIETI data
α_{l}^{e}	sharing energy services distribution parameter	-	0.15536	Model's First Order Conditions, E-stat and RIETI databases
α_{l}^{e*}	home-produced energy services distribution parameter	-	0.92291	Model's First Order Conditions
α_{l}^{e**}	new durable goods investments distribution parameter	-	0.96410	Model's First Order Conditions, OECD and RIETI data
α_{l}^{e***}	repaired durable goods investments distribution parameter	-	0.70093	Model's First Order Conditions, OECD and RIETI data
α_{el}^{e}	durable goods distribution parameter	-	5.82550	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
α_{el}^{e*}	Households' energy distribution parameter	-	0.01145	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
α_{el}^{e**}	Households' electricity distribution parameter	-	0.26875	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, E-stat, OECD and RIETI databases
α_{el}^{e***}	Households' fuels distribution parameter	-	0.44195	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, E-stat, OECD and RIETI databases
α_{el}^{e****}	secondary material producing firm's electricity input distribution parameter	-	0.63458	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
α_{el}^{e*****}	secondary material producing firm's fuel input distribution parameter	-	0.13042	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
α_{el}^{e*****}	secondary material producing firm's electricity input distribution parameter	-	0.17589	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
α_{prim}^{e}	primary material producing firm's electricity input distribution parameter	-	0.55813	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
α_{prim}^{e*}	primary material producing firm's fuel input distribution parameter	-	0.48735	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
$\alpha_{capital}^{e}$	capital good producing firm's electricity input distribution parameter	-	0.22742	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
$\alpha_{capital}^{e*}$	capital good producing firm's fuel input distribution parameter	-	0.67015	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
$\alpha_{ndurable}^{e}$	durable good producing firm's electricity input distribution parameter	-	0.11103	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
$\alpha_{ndurable}^{e*}$	durable good producing firm's fuel input distribution parameter	-	0.65701	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
$\alpha_{semdurable}^{e}$	semi-durable good producing firm's electricity input distribution parameter	-	0.11802	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
$\alpha_{semdurable}^{e*}$	semi-durable good producing firm's fuel input distribution parameter	-	0.14591	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
$\alpha_{ndurable}^{e**}$	non-durable good producing firm's electricity input distribution parameter	-	0.60531	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
$\alpha_{ndurable}^{e***}$	non-durable good producing firm's fuel input distribution parameter	-	0.26865	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, E-stat, OECD and RIETI databases
α_{share}^{e}	sharing services producing firm's electricity input distribution parameter	-		

Table B6: Calibration of CIRCEE (continued)

Parameter	Description	Unit	Value	Source of data
α_{fuel}^{prime}	sharing services producing firm's fuel input distribution parameter	-	0.44195	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, E-stat, OECD and RIETI databases
$\alpha_{non-durable}^{prime}$	non-durable good producing firm's primary materials input distribution parameter	-	0.61348	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI data, Ministry of the Environment's data, Resource Panel database, GLORIA database of [34] and [35]
$\alpha_{semi-durable}^{prime}$	semi-durable good producing firm's primary materials input distribution parameter	-	0.70918	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI data, Ministry of the Environment's data, Resource Panel database, GLORIA database of [34] and [35]
$\alpha_{durable}^{prime}$	durable good producing firm's primary materials input distribution parameter	-	0.73260	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI data, Ministry of the Environment's data, Resource Panel database, GLORIA database of [34] and [35]
$\alpha_{capital}^{prime}$	capital good producing firm's primary materials input distribution parameter	-	0.31438	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI data, Ministry of the Environment's data, Resource Panel database, GLORIA database of [34] and [35]
$\alpha_{non-durable}^{second}$	non-durable good producing firm's secondary materials input distribution parameter	-	3.58757E-07	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI data, Ministry of the Environment's data, Resource Panel database, GLORIA database of [34] and [35]
$\alpha_{semi-durable}^{second}$	semi-durable good producing firm's secondary materials input distribution parameter	-	5.01336E-08	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI data, Ministry of the Environment's data, Resource Panel database, GLORIA database of [34] and [35]
$\alpha_{durable}^{second}$	durable good producing firm's secondary materials input distribution parameter	-	5.47453E-08	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI data, Ministry of the Environment's data, Resource Panel database, GLORIA database of [34] and [35]
$\alpha_{capital}^{second}$	capital good producing firm's secondary materials input distribution parameter	-	1.31986E-05	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI data, Ministry of the Environment's data, Resource Panel database, GLORIA database of [34] and [35]

Table B7: Calibration of CIRCEE (continued)

Exogenous variable	Description	Unit	Value	Source of data
A_{labor}	Labor productivity	-	1	model's assumption
$A_{p_n}^n$	Material productivity	-	1	model's assumption
δ^k	capital good depreciation rate	-	0.06668	RIETI data
δ_{fix}^d	durable good depreciation rate	-	0.09516	of [60] and [61]
δ_{fix}^s	semi-durable good depreciation rate	-	0.08357	[62]
δ_{sd}	V.A.T. tax on repair services	-	0.092	OECD-stat and RIETI
$\tau_{reduced}$	firms' electricity excise tax	-	0.01096	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
τ_{el}^d	households' electricity excise tax	-	0	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, E-stat, OECD and RIETI databases
τ_{el}^s	repair bonus	-	0	model's assumption
τ_{el}^h	use rate of durable goods	-	0.97	[63], [64], [65], [66], [67], [68], [69]
τ_{el}^u	share of lowcarbon household in total population	-	0.69046	LIFE model of [13]
u	share of cautious household in total population	-	0.15693	LIFE model of [13]
$w_{lowcarbon}$	green product design cost parameter	-	0	model's assumption
$\xi_{prede sign}$	semi-durable good EPR fee as a share of the final price	-	0.00329	Ministry of the Economy and Industry, [70]
fee_{epr}	durable goods EPR fee as a share of the final price	-	0.04131	Ministry of the Economy and Industry, [70]
$fee_{durable}$	access fee to the digital platform charged by the sharing firm	-	0.25	[71] and [72]
$fee_{platform}$	sharing income taxation	-	0.31957	National Tax Agency, OECD-stat and RIETI data
τ_{import}	capital goods import tariff	-	0.00221	International Trade Administration and TransCustoms
$\tau_{capital}$	non-durable goods import tariff	-	0.04398	International Trade Administration and TransCustoms
τ_{import}^n	semi-durable goods import tariff	-	0.03202	International Trade Administration and TransCustoms
τ_{import}^s	durable goods import tariff	-	0	International Trade Administration and TransCustoms
$\tau_{import}^{durable}$	collection and transportation cost	-	0.00217	Ministry of the Environment
$\tau_{import}^{semidurable}$	Electricity efficiency of the recycling sector	JPY per gram	1.04154	WITCH model [51]
$\tau_{import}^{collection}$	Fuel efficiency of the recycling sector	-	1.02206	WITCH model [51]
A_{el}	households' gross electricity price	-	5.34200	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, E-stat, OECD and RIETI databases
A_{el}^d	households' fuel tax	JPY per MJ	0.87209	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, E-stat, OECD and RIETI databases
A_{el}^s	households' gross fuel price	JPY per MJ	2.36929	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, E-stat, OECD and RIETI databases
p_{el}^d	firms' gross electricity price	JPY per MJ	4.90882	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
p_{el}^s	firms' fuel tax	JPY per MJ	0.52497	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
p_{el}	firms' gross fuel price	JPY per MJ	1.93214	Model's First Order Conditions, Agency for Natural Resources and Energy, OECD and RIETI databases
$material_{int}^{nondurable}$	material intensity of non-durable goods imports	-	0.18335	Resource Panel and RIETI database
$material_{int}^{semidurable}$	material intensity of semi-durable goods imports	-	0.18335	Resource Panel and RIETI database
$material_{int}^{durable}$	material intensity of durable goods imports	-	0.18335	Resource Panel and RIETI database
$material_{int}^{capital}$	material intensity of capital goods imports	-	0.18335	Resource Panel and RIETI database
p_{prim}	primary material gross price	JPY per gram	0.04130	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI, Ministry of the Environment, Resource Panel database and Gloria database of [34] and [35]
p_{sec}	secondary material gross price	JPY per gram	0.05259	Model's First Order Conditions, RIETI, Ministry of the Environment, Resource Panel database and Gloria database of [34] and [35]
$\gamma_{durable}$	material loss during the production process of durable goods	-	0.03101	Ministry of the Environment, Resource Panel database and RIETI databases
$\gamma_{semidurable}$	material loss during the production process of semi-durable goods	-	0.03934	Ministry of the Environment, Resource Panel and RIETI databases
$\gamma_{nondurable}$	material loss during the production process of non-durable goods	-	0.05158	Ministry of the Environment, Resource Panel and RIETI databases
$\gamma_{capital}$	material loss during the production process of capital goods	-	0.12398	Ministry of the Environment, Resource Panel and RIETI databases
γ_{prim}	material loss during the production process of primary materials	-	0.08062	Ministry of the Environment, Resource Panel and RIETI databases
γ_{sec}	material loss during the production process of secondary materials	-	0.04061	Ministry of the Environment, Resource Panel and RIETI databases
$\omega_{municip}$	share of recycled waste in total municipal waste	-	0.19659	Ministry of the Environment, Resource Panel and RIETI databases
$\omega_{ind}^{recycled}$	share of recycled waste in total industrial waste	-	0.58393	Ministry of the Environment, Resource Panel and RIETI databases
τ_{ind}^{waste}	landfilled industrial waste tax	JPY per gram	0.00090	Ministry of the Environment, [73]
$\tau_{municip}$	municipal waste tax	JPY per gram	0.05610	Ministry of the Environment
τ_{raw}	foreign demand of materials	JPY per gram	0.11427	Ministry of the Environment, Resource Panel, GLORIA database of [34] and [35] and RIETI database
$share_{foreign}$	price of raw materials	JPY per gram	0.00563	Ministry of the Environment, Resource Panel, GLORIA database of [34] and [35] and RIETI database

Table B8: Exogenous variables in CIRCÉE for the base year 2018